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**THE RELATIONSHIP OF INFORMAL DIGITAL LEARNING OF ENGLISH
WITH THE VOCABULARY AND WRITING DEVELOPMENT
OF FILIPINO SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **MARIA ALEXIA A. ADIZON** with the title: “**THE RELATIONSHIP OF INFORMAL DIGITAL LEARNING OF ENGLISH WITH THE VOCABULARY AND WRITING DEVELOPMENT OF FILIPINO SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education.

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my family, my friends and colleagues, my students past and present, and above all, to God Almighty.

ABSTRACT

Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) refers to the informal, self-directed English learning using different digital devices (e.g., smartphones, laptops) and resources (e.g., apps, social media) independent of formal contexts. This study examined what IDLE activities Filipino senior high school students are engaged in and investigated whether the time spent on these activities had any correlation with their (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance. It also looked into how IDLE activities affect the students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. This research used quantitative methods including a survey and vocabulary and writing tests among 99 SHS students from Bacolod City, and qualitative methods, namely interviews among selected participants from the sample and their family members. This study demonstrates that the participants engage in a variety of IDLE activities, with the presence of multitasking and parental influence. However, the time they spend on these had no significant correlation with their vocabulary and writing performance. Even with a lack of correlation among the variables, the interview participants cited the different ways how IDLE activities had contributed to their vocabulary knowledge, which may be attributed to their engagement in form- and meaning-focused language learning. Moreover, the results indicate the possibility that the participants' writing errors were caused by the informal English, slang, and errors in English that they were exposed to online. However, the interview participants still identified the positive influence of IDLE on their writing, such as providing models of good writing. Educators and parents may consider integrating IDLE in their children's learning of English.

Keywords: Informal Digital Learning of English, Vocabulary, Writing

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Informal language learning refers to “any activities taken consciously or unconsciously by a learner outside of formal instruction that lead to an increase in the learner’s ability to communicate in a second (or other, non-native) language” (Dressman & Sadler, 2019, p.4). Because of the internet and digital technologies, people can learn a language through YouTube or commercial platforms such as Babbel and Duolingo. They can interact with other players who speak English on social networking sites, online forums, and/or massively multiplayer online role-playing games or MMORPGs (Dressman, 2020). Lee and Dressman (2018) called these activities Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE), defining it as “self-directed, informal English learning using a range of different digital devices (e.g., smartphones, desktop computers) and resources (e.g., web apps, social media) independent of formal contexts.” (p. 1).

IDLE matters because young people, including Filipinos, are significantly exposed to digital technologies (Nagata et al., 2021). According to UNICEF's report, *The State of the World's Children 2017: Children in a Digital World*, one in three internet users is younger than 18 years old, and 71% of 15-24-year-olds are online. Young people are the most connected age group online (The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health, 2018). In the Philippines, the 2019 survey by the Social Weather Station (SWS) found that 86% of the 18–24-year-old respondents surveyed were Internet users, which is the highest among the age groups (Nazario et al., 2019). According to other surveys, young Filipinos use the internet for social media, research

work, and email (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2020). Although too much screen time may have harmful effects on children and adolescents (Serrano, 2022), the internet and digital technologies have been shown to have positive influence in young people's language learning.

Given the youth's exposure to digital technologies, recent research has looked into how this has affected second language acquisition and learning. Adolescents are continuously engaged with technology, changing the way they learn, even outside the classroom. English learners are increasingly exposed to authentic English language because of high-speed internet and available online tools (Yurieva et al., 2021). Technology has also played a significant role in informal language learning.

Since 2010 up to the present, digital devices have become smaller, more diverse, and more powerful. They allow people to access second language learning anytime and anywhere, giving them more opportunities to improve in and practice the second language (Lee, 2021). Studies have shown that IDLE-oriented activities are positively associated with second language outcomes, such as the linguistic aspects (e.g., vocabulary and speaking), affective aspects (e.g., motivation and enjoyment), and formal language test scores (Cole & Vanderplank, 2016; Dressman & Sadler, 2020; Sockett, 2014; Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2016). Time spent on IDLE activities has also been associated with vocabulary performance (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019). Likewise, frequency spent on IDLE has been associated with writing proficiency (Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015; Olsson, 2016)

Among the second language outcomes, vocabulary improves other communication skills such as speaking, reading, and writing (Seifert, 2016). It can predict reading success and academic achievement (Ferrer & Carmen, 2022). The

vocabulary knowledge of children and adults is strongly associated with their reading comprehension (Caroll, 1993, as cited Cain, 2014). According to Rasinki and Rupley (2019), readers who know the meaning of the words in the text are more likely to understand what they are reading. Proficient readers typically have an extensive vocabulary. Vocabulary is required for “background knowledge, concepts about the world, understanding discipline content, integration of new learning with what is known, and representation of abstract understandings” (p. ix). Learners’ breadth and depth of vocabulary affect their interaction and comprehension of what they read. The need for vocabulary knowledge increases as students get older (Fisher & Frey, 2014). Late adolescent English language learners may have difficulties in the pronunciation, spelling, and usage of new vocabulary and guessing the meanings from the context, among other issues. Problems like these may weaken the students’ reading comprehension, writing, and other communication skills because of a lack of vocabulary knowledge (Afzal, 2019). Moreover, second language learners not only need to know a lot of words, but know them well enough to use them well in writing. They would need to know its form, meaning, and use in writing (Brun-Mercer & Zimmerman, 2015; Nation, 2013).

It would therefore be useful to investigate the relationship of IDLE with the vocabulary development of adolescent second language learners. IDLE activities may help with these issues in vocabulary learning because learners are largely exposed to authentic written and spoken input in English from various sources outside school, which can lead to vocabulary learning. Increased Informal Digital Learning of English has generally demonstrated a positive relationship with second language learners’ vocabulary acquisition. Frequency and diversity in IDLE activities were both linked to

the vocabulary scores of second language learners (Lee, 2020, 2019; Lee & Dressman, 2018; Sundqvist, 2019, Peters, 2018; Jensen, 2017; Puimège & Peters, 2019). For instance, learners can acquire vocabulary through frequent digital gaming or watching YouTube videos. Moreover, a learner playing an English game can learn the vocabulary, expressions, and knowledge relevant to the game through YouTube, blogs, and online communities (Lee, 2021).

IDLE can also be associated with writing, a skill that many students find difficult. According to the National Institute for Literacy (n.d.), writing development requires the reinforcement of reading skills and direct, explicit, and systematic instruction. Adolescents can also develop their writing skills through practice, writing for different audiences, and having many opportunities to read (Colorín Colorado, 2016). Struggling learners may find it difficult to organize their ideas, use the mechanics of writing, come up with the right words to communicate ideas, and lack fluency in developing ideas, among other problems (Richards, 1999, as cited in Colorín Colorado, 2016). Informal Digital Learning of English may help address these issues because learners immerse themselves in authentic English text through reading and writing using digital technologies and the internet. According to Zheng and Lin (2019), a growing body of research shows that digital media could provide opportunities for second language learners to practice and improve their writing for English-speaking audiences. Writing in digital settings helps learners develop their identities as L2 writers, develop motivation and autonomy in writing, and give them access to interaction and feedback from other individuals worldwide. Technology-supported writing outside school, namely through gaming, has been found to help enhance

second language learners' vocabulary and language complexity, which are both needed for writing (Scholz, 2015).

While digital technology has been effective in the English learning of students in other countries, in the Philippine context, the present study may be relevant to the teaching of vocabulary and writing, because recent international assessments reveal that Filipino students scored just the minimum proficiency in reading and writing in the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019, 60% of whom have “limited vocabulary” (Balinbin, 2020). Another assessment showed that Filipino students, who scored lowest in reading comprehension among 79 countries in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (San Juan, 2019). Many senior high school and college students in the country lack the vocabulary knowledge in English needed for speaking and writing (Dadola, et al., 2020; Calub & Calub, 2017). Moreover, Filipino high school students have shown problems in writing, particularly in grammar and mechanics (Hikmah, et al., 2019), and according to a report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2020), “some senior high school students (SHS) cannot even write a decent English sentence.” Conducting Informal Digital Learning of English in the Philippine setting may lead to new insights about informal vocabulary and writing development, which can supplement classroom instruction.

There are existing studies in the Philippines about using digital resources such as YouTube and Facebook in English language learning in the classroom (Caipang et al., 2021; Arnobit et al., 2018; Mabuan & Ebron, 2016). Philippine research has recognized the potential of digital resources for language learning. However, there is little local research about informal learning of English using digital resources

(Bayugan, 2017). Moreover, most of the studies relating IDLE to vocabulary have been conducted in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) settings (Lee, 2017; Lee & Dressman; 2017; Lee, 2019; Peter, Noreille, et al., 2019; Shafirova & Cassany, 2019; Mohammed & Ali; 2021). Hence, this present study was done in an English as a Second Language (ESL) context, the Philippines. It aims to investigate the relationship between Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) with the vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of Filipino senior high school second language learners. The results of this study have implications for integrating IDLE into teaching English and developing strategies for teaching vocabulary and writing using this resource.

Today's adolescents, including Filipinos, have increased exposure to digital technologies such as the internet, laptops, and smartphones (Gonzales, 2020). Because of this, previous research has investigated Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE), which refers to how English learners learn the language in a self-directed, informal manner using digital devices and resources (Lee & Dressman, 2018). Studies have associated IDLE activities with second language and literacy outcomes, such as vocabulary and writing skills (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Olsson, 2016; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019).

This research placed this field of study in the Philippines and investigated the relationship between IDLE and the vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of Filipino senior high school students. Through the study of IDLE, this thesis aims to achieve a better understanding of how the students can learn vocabulary knowledge and writing skills outside the classroom using informal, digital means. Another objective is to provide insights for students, parents, and educators about how the informal, leisurely

use of the internet and digital technologies can be used to augment students' English language learning.

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of the study was to investigate the IDLE activities of Filipino senior high school students and the relationship between the time spent on these activities and (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance. Specifically, I asked the following questions:

1. What Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) activities are Filipino senior high school students engaged in?
2. Is there a correlation between the time spent on IDLE activities of Filipino senior high school students and their:
 - a. Vocabulary performance?
 - b. Writing performance?
3. In what ways do IDLE activities affect senior high school students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills?

Significance of the Study

This study about the relationship between Filipino senior high school students' IDLE activities and their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills may benefit English teachers, researchers, and students.

ESL Teachers. This study may benefit teachers because upon knowing the benefits of IDLE, they can purposefully integrate IDLE activities in formal instruction.

ESL Learners. This study can benefit Filipino learners by investigating alternative ways to learn English vocabulary and writing outside the classroom. It can further validate the role of informal language learning in the second language acquisition of Filipino students. Knowing the effectiveness of IDLE may motivate them to continue engaging in IDLE activities and experiment with other forms of IDLE that they have not tried before, maximizing IDLE to learn English.

Researchers. This study can contribute to research about IDLE and its value to second language teaching in the Philippine context, specifically in the area of vocabulary and writing development. Researchers can use this study to investigate further the potentials of IDLE in language acquisition and its relationship to different language and literacy outcomes. This study also presents implications for language teaching, of how IDLE can be integrated into instruction.

Scope and Delimitations

This study aims to investigate the relationship between Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) and the vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of Filipino senior high school students. IDLE involves the engagement in digital activities only in English. The IDLE activities that were considered in this study are: (1) watching online videos, (2) listening to music, (3) using social media, (4) reading digital content, (5) digital gaming, and (6) reading and/or writing on social reading platforms like Wattpad. It can be concluded that these IDLE activities are done by a significant percentage of

young Filipinos because the proportion of internet users is highest among this age group (Nazario et al., 2019).

This research focused on relating time spent on IDLE with vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, respectively. Because vocabulary knowledge and writing skills are both important for Filipino senior high school students, this research explores how IDLE influences these.

The participants were senior high school Grade 12 students, who are 17-18 years old. They are English as Second Language learners, as they speak Hiligaynon as a mother tongue, and English as another language, which is the predominant medium of instruction at their school, and it is widely spoken in both private and public domain. They also have access to the internet and devices such as smartphones and laptops. Grade 12 students were also born around the time of the birth of Web 2.0 back in 2004 (Hosch, 2022). Many of them spent most of their lives exposed to social networking, digital games, eBooks, among the other affordances of the Internet. Furthermore, senior high school students are required to take the subject Media and Information Literacy as part of their SHS curriculum, which teaches them to be responsible users of media and information, which includes their use of internet and digital technologies.

Some of the instruments in this thesis were developed and adapted from ones used in other studies. I opted to do this and not to use the existing ones so that I could answer the specific research questions and make the instruments suitable for research locale. For instance, instead of asking for the frequency of IDLE activities as previous researchers have done, I developed an instrument to ask the actual time the participants spent on IDLE because this is what is asked for by my formulated research

questions. I also modified the vocabulary test by conducting an item analysis after a pilot test to select items of acceptable difficulty and discrimination indices, unlike previous researchers who just used existing versions of the test. Moreover, for the writing test I developed, I asked questions about internet and social media use that are appropriate for the participants in Generation Z. I developed and adapted my study's instruments based on existing ones to make them fit for the research question and to make them appropriate for the research participants.

Conducting this research took a whole year and was affected by the constraints of the COVID-19 pandemic. During this period, the participants had online classes to prevent the spread of the virus. In the quantitative phase of the study, I could not administer the research instruments face-to-face because of the pandemic, so I borrowed online class periods from their teachers and proctored the tests via Google Meet and Google Forms. In the qualitative phase of the study, I interviewed the participants through voice calls to avoid the spread of the virus. To maintain the validity of the data, I proctored all the online data gathering sessions and gave them clear instructions on how to answer the research instruments within the time limit. It was also clear to them that participating in this study had no bearing on their grades at school, so they had no motivation to cheat in answering the tests.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Review of Related Literature and Conceptual Framework

This chapter begins with an introduction to IDLE, its related concepts, its underlying principles, and an overview of adolescent learners' exposure to IDLE. Afterward, I summarize IDLE and language and literacy learning outcomes in general. Then, I focus on the development of vocabulary knowledge and writing skills and the relationship between these skills and IDLE. The review ends with a synthesis of the variables of IDLE and vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Informal Digital Learning of English

Definition of IDLE and its Types

Ju Seong Lee coined the term Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) during his research on informal language learning in Morocco and Korea (Lee, 2021). He defined IDLE as a “self-directed, naturalistic, digital learning of English in unstructured, out-of-class environments, independent of a formal language program” (Lee, 2019, p.116). It involves the use of different digital devices (e.g., smartphones, laptops) and resources (e.g., social media, websites) (Lee & Dressman, 2018). Lee, Xie, and Lee (2021) also observed that with IDLE, learners “are engaged independently without being evaluated by a language teacher” (p. 3). IDLE learners consume English content using different modalities, like texts, audio, images, and video, which help them understand and learn the target language. Nowadays, learners learn and use English through various online sources like dictionaries, news websites, social media, online forums, online games, email, eBooks, movies, songs, drama and comedy series,

Google, and YouTube. When learners use a range of digital resources, this multimodality can support their English learning (Lee, 2021). For example, English language learners may develop their speaking skills with other game players during a massively multiplayer online role-playing game (MMORPG). They can also learn the language by reading online content such as comics or travel literature.

IDLE can be situated under the broader field of *Language Learning Beyond the Classroom* (LBC). LBC is the general term used to describe language learning outside school using various means, like engaging in information and communication technology or traveling to other countries. LBC considers both offline (e.g., language ‘cafes’ in schools, self-organized English communities) and online settings (e.g., social media, fan fiction, online series) (Reinders & Benson, 2017).

There are concepts like IDLE made by other researchers that show how this phenomenon occurs in different countries and contexts. The first is *informal second language learning* (ISLL) which was explored by Arndt and Woore (2018) when they studied the English vocabulary acquisition of different EFL learners. Like IDLE, this term covers informal learning primarily through different online media like music and television series. The researchers used the concept of incidental learning by Hulstijn, which refers to “the acquisition of a word or expression without the conscious intention to commit the element to memory, such as ‘picking up’ an unknown word from listening to someone or from reading a text.” (Hulstijn, 2013, p. 1). With this concept, the researchers deduced that the EFL learners were able to incidentally learn vocabulary from online media. Another similar concept is *Online Informal Learning of English* (OILE), which was coined by Sockett and Toffoli (2010) during their study of French university students’ contact with online English. Like IDLE, OILE refers to the informal

learning of English through Web 2.0 technologies, such as social networking, watching films and series, sending emails, and reading or writing blogs (Jurkovič, 2019; Toffoli, 2020).

Other IDLE-related concepts consider both online and offline means of learning English informally, such as *Extramural English* (EE), *Fully Autonomous Self-Instructed Learners* (FASIL), and recreational language learning. *Extramural English* (EE) was coined by Pia Sundqvist (2009) during her study of Swedish ESL teenagers' engagement in English-mediated activities outside school and its relationship to their vocabulary and oral proficiency. Extramural English refers to the English that learners are exposed to or are involved in outside the classroom walls. She coined this while studying Swedish students. Like IDLE and OILE, EE includes reading English websites on the internet, following accounts on Twitter and Instagram, and playing digital games. Unlike IDLE, EE also involves offline activities like reading books, magazines, and newspapers (Sundqvist, 2016). The researchers used the concept of learner autonomy, or "the ability to take charge of one's own learning" (Holec, 1981, p.3, as cited in Sundqvist & Sylven, 2016) to underpin the study of Extramural English because some second language learners take charge of their own learning. Similarly, Cole and Vanderplank (2016) used the term *Fully Autonomous Self-Instructed Learners* (FASIL) to describe Brazilian students learning English during a study about autonomous and class-based learners. FASILs are learners who acquire English by engaging with informal language sources, such as the internet and television. Like IDLE, the construct includes digital resources such as the Internet, but unlike IDLE, it also includes offline resources like television. FASILs demonstrated higher English language scores than learners who were just taught English in the classroom. Chik

and Ho (2017) contributed to the field as well, using the term *recreational language learning*. They operationalized the term while studying three language learners in Hong Kong who were learning non-English languages using free public resources. Recreational language learning is not done for school or work but for leisure. Like IDLE, research on recreational language learning focuses on how greater online access to learning resources and communities enables second language learners to recreationally learn a language for free. These resources include Duolingo, YouTube, online dictionaries and newspapers, and interaction with native speakers through blog writing.

Informal language learning, especially in online and digital settings, has been studied under different concepts and in other countries and contexts. Research in the field has been underpinned by existing concepts in language learning, such as incidental learning (Hulstijn, 2013) and learner autonomy (Holec, 1981, as cited in Lee, 2017), which are both relevant to the present study. The growing research in this field shows the trend of language learning beyond the classroom. Among the different concepts, I chose IDLE as a framework because it focuses on the informal learning of English through digital means in out-of-class settings (Lee, 2019), omitting offline and analog means. IDLE also exemplifies the elements of leisure and implicit acquisition (Toffoli, 2020). This present paper is an opportunity to situate the phenomenon of Informal Digital Learning of English in the Philippines, a country with an Internet user penetration of 72.7% (Statista, 2020).

Furthermore, English language learners typically engage in two types of IDLE: receptive IDLE activities (RIA) and productive IDLE activities (PIA) (Lee & Drajeti, 2019). RIA involves understanding something in English (e.g., watching English

movies or series, listening to English songs, listening to English language news programs online). On the other hand, PIA is concerned with producing English communication (e.g., direct messaging on Facebook, sharing YouTube videos, sending English emails to others, chatting with foreigners in English, posting English comments on a friend's Facebook wall).

Second Language Learning

According to Rieder-Bünemann (2012), second language learning refers to how people acquire a second language (L2 or the target language). One of the most common languages spoken as a second language is English. English as a Second Language (ESL) refers to the use or study of English by non-native speakers in an English-speaking environment (Nordquist, 2019).

A second language can be any language learned in addition to the native language or L1. Some researchers distinguish between acquisition and learning; acquisition is referred to as the “gradual subconscious development of language abilities by using the language naturally” (p.2980), while learning is the conscious accumulation of knowledge of a language, usually as the product of formal instruction (Krashen, 1982). The term second language learning is also sometimes specifically used for the learning of languages through formal instruction, while second language acquisition is generally used as a generic term to refer to learning the L2 in all contexts, including the classroom (Rieder-Bünemann, 2012). Second language acquisition and learning can occur in formal and informal contexts.

In informal settings, second language learning happens when learners are exposed to the target language at home, work, or in social interactions. It can also

occur when learners use different technologies through watching a movie or listening to music which provide appropriate and authentic language input (Lightbown & Spada, 2001, as cited in Bahrani & Nekoueizadeh, 2014). Learners need to be exposed to the language both inside and outside the classroom to be able to learn it (González & Fàbregas, 2021).

Digital Activities and English Language Learning

According to previous literature, there are certain digital activities which have been found to influence English language learning, namely social media, digital reading, podcasts, and synchronous video computer-mediated communication.

Social Media. Social media has positive and negative effects on language learning. Social media has impacted language learning because it may negatively affect grammar, spelling, and sentence construction by exposing the learners to errors in writing (Saha, 2019). However, other learners experienced improvement in their writing style, reading skills, lexical variation, communication skills because of social media (Muftah, 2022; Haque, 2018).

Social media, especially Facebook, is a major source of English news. Other platforms include YouTube, Twitter, and Instagram (Martin, 2018). The news are authentic resources of language learning (Roberts, 2014). Reading the news has been found to enhance vocabulary, grammar, idioms, and phrases (Sultana & Singh, 2022; Preethi, 2020).

Digital Reading. Digital or online reading is fundamentally different from reading print materials (Nordquist, 2017) because it is “nonlinear;” when one reads information digitally, they can go to other sources using hyperlinks (Carter, 2013, as

cited by Nordquist, 2017). These help the student deepen their understanding or learn the definition of new or confusing terms (Hurt, 2023).

Podcasts. Podcasts can positively affect English language learning, specifically listening comprehension (Abdulrahman, et al., 2018). Moreover, one can learn a language while listening to podcasts while doing tasks that do not require much concentration (Koyfman, 2019).

Synchronous Video Computer-Mediated Communication (SVMC). SVMC includes platforms such as Skype, FaceTime, and Zoom, which connects second language learners with speakers of the target language. SVMC gives the learner opportunities to interact in the second language, receiving input and producing input, which are needed for language development (Kessler, et al., 2021).

Factors Affecting IDLE

IDLE and Multitasking

A factor that may affect IDLE is multitasking, which refers to simultaneously accessing two or more forms of media (Becker et al., 2013a). Teenagers average over 11 hours of daily media consumption in multitasking, which is 29% of total media time. Multitasking with media significantly increased during the 2000s because of the increase in the use of information and communication technologies. Multitasking in these activities include watching videos on a computer, listening to music, video or computer games, using the phone, chatting, and other computer applications (Uncapher & Wagner, 2018). According to Godwin-Jones (2019), multitasking in IDLE can likewise occur when learners listen to music while reading lyrics online at the same time or when they watch movies or television programs while reading subtitles.

Multitasking can also affect language learning depending on whether the person is multitasking to distract oneself, or they are multitasking in an informed or intentional way. A learner who engages in distracted multitasking may recall fewer words than a person with no distractions (Middlebrooks, et al., 2017). On the other hand, multitasking mindfully while learning a language can be productive by studying while exercising or listening to podcasts while doing activities that do not require mental concentration, like household tasks (Koyfman, 2019).

IDLE and Parental Influence on Children's Technology Use

Moreover, IDLE may also be affected by the influence of parents on their children's technology use. As primary educators of their children, parents may give their children access to devices and the internet, and regulate their children's use of technology by guiding them to use it appropriately and safely (Office of Educational Technology, n.d.). Digital learning resources which are provided by parents are an important element of learners' language exposure, which then influences their feelings and motivation about learning English (Lee & Lee, 2020, as cited in Tiao & Xu, 2022). In Korea, parents support their children to achieve Korean-English bilingualism, through, for example, using books, television, animation, and YouTube (Nam, 2016; Seo, 2018 as cited in Lee, 2021). Lindgren and Munoz (2013) investigated the impact of out-of-school factors on young European learners' listening and reading skills in a second language, and found that the learner's parents expose their children to a second language at home by watching TV/films, listening to music, or browsing the internet. This exposure was a strong predictor of the learners' listening and reading scores. The findings suggest that parents who expose their children to a second

language through online and digital means can facilitate their learning of that language. In the Philippines, Soriano and Garcia (2021) investigated how exposure to the English through media, technology, and the home helped students with their English lessons. The researchers found that parents were a big factor in their exposure to the language, as they would expose their children to English media such as films.

Informal English and IDLE

Another factor that affects IDLE is informal English. Much of the English content on the internet consists of slang, which is nonstandard, informal vocabulary that includes newly coined words, shortcuts, and standard words used out of their usual context (Maurer, 2021). For example, Generation Z in particular have used the terms “slay” which means someone has done a job or task exceptionally well (Hart, 2022), or “glow-up” to describe how someone improved from how they used to be (Seariac, 2022). Moreover, on the internet, there have been many changes in verbal and non-verbal means of communication, such as abbreviations, spelling changes, grammatical and spelling mistakes, and emojis used by young people (Barseghyan, 2013). While slang can facilitate communication in informal contexts online, it is avoided in academic writing (Purdue OWL, n.d.).

Funmilayo (2020) investigated the effect of internet slang on the English essay writing of Nigerian secondary school students by surveying them about how internet slang increases grammatical errors. 75% of the sample agreed that internet slang increases the grammatical errors in writing among English language students. These results show that informal forms of English may affect the informal language learning of students.

The Underlying Principles of IDLE

Recent studies about informal language learning suggest that online materials and communities in multiple languages are so abundant, affordable, and attractive that Godwin-Jones (2019) claims that it “obviates the necessity to learn an L2 in a classroom setting” (p. 6). Nowadays, English learners engage in IDLE using these online materials and communities, which can complement the limitations of formal education in English. Lee (2021) presents underlying principles why:

Accessibility. In recent years, digital devices (e.g., laptops and cellphones) and digital content (e.g., Instagram posts and YouTube videos) have become more affordable and engaging. There is an abundance of texts, images, sounds, animation, and videos being created and shared in English on the internet. Learners can access English content anytime and anywhere, even outside class, as long as they have an internet connection. English is available 24/7 through IDLE.

In the context of the Philippines, a Pulse Asia survey in 2021 showed that 63 percent of adult Filipinos had access to the internet (U.S. Embassy in the Philippines, 2022), while 75.3% of the Philippine population have smartphones (Statista, 2021). Filipinos also spend up to 10 hours a day using the internet (Statista, 2021), and English is the most popular language online (Johnson, 2022). A large amount of English input, so accessible through the Internet, may influence the language acquisition of Filipino learners.

Motivation. IDLE learners are intrinsically motivated to learn English because of their interest and enjoyment in learning. For example, Nanquil (2020) observed in his study with Filipino college students that they use Facebook to look for interesting

information in English, such as social and environmental issues, updates about their friends and relatives, and news and gossip—mainly in English.

Authenticity. Through IDLE, English learners have access to authentic input of English that can be used in real life. For instance, when students listen to songs on SoundCloud, watch YouTube videos, or play MMPORGs, they can be exposed to the natural English pronunciation. Moreover, they can communicate with other English users by writing English comments on YouTube or SoundCloud or talking with other MMORPG players. They also get to receive feedback in English that is genuine and immediate.

Identity and investment. Because of IDLE, English learners often develop a new identity as English users. Over time, they consistently use English using digital resources, becoming authentic English users, not just learners (Sockett & Toffoli, 2012). Lee (2021) noted the example of a Korean EFL amateur rapper who creates and uploads English rap songs to SoundCloud, Instagram, and Facebook hip-hop communities, where he has many followers. Because he wants to write more and better English rap songs, he develops his English skills even further. To do this, he reads and listens to more English.

Flow. When learners occupy themselves with IDLE activities, like playing online games in English, watching Netflix in English, or chatting with friends in English, they usually fully enjoy them. They end up experiencing being “in the zone” or the flow state, which refers to the state of mind when a person becomes fully immersed in an activity (Csíkszentmihályi, 1997, as cited in Cherry, 2021). When engaging in IDLE, learners often lose track of time and become so immersed in the activity because they

are minimally anxious and are enjoying themselves. They also receive immediate, personalized feedback for their English speaking and writing skills.

Grit. Grit is “passion and perseverance for long-term goals” (Duckworth, 2007). IDLE learners have to be gritty because they learn with minimal or no guidance. They are also often passionate about their IDLE activities, so they are inclined to continue their interests. They usually continue their effort in learning and practicing English despite the difficulties. The Korean amateur rapper mentioned earlier has a lot of grit since he practices independently and repeatedly to improve his English skills to write better hip-hop songs.

Intentional and unintentional learning. Acquiring and learning the English language through IDLE can happen incidentally and intentionally. For example, vocabulary can be developed incidentally by online gaming or YouTube videos. At the same time, English language learners can also learn vocabulary intentionally through media consumption and online gaming. For example, a Korean EFL learner and StarCraft gamer may deliberately learn the vocabulary, expressions, and knowledge connected to the game using YouTube videos, blogs, and discussions within online communities.

Theoretical Underpinnings of IDLE

The following theories of learning underpin IDLE—*incidental learning* (Hulstijn, 2013), *learner autonomy* (Holec, 1981, as cited in Lee, 2017), the *Affective Filter hypothesis* (Krashen, 1982), and the *New Literacies Theory* (Buckingham, 1993).

Incidental learning. IDLE is theoretically supported by *incidental learning* (Hulstijn, 2013) which is the acquisition of words or expressions without consciously

intending to commit them to memory. This can happen, for example, when a learner “picks up” a new word while listening to someone or reading a text in the target language (Hulstijn, 2012). Researchers in this field posit that language learning involves incidental vocabulary acquisition in everyday activities (Sockett, 2014) and that it requires “attention to the stimuli but does not require conscious processing.” (Rieder, 2003, as cited in Sockett, 2014). This is evident in informal language learning using online and digital resources because learners may incidentally pick up vocabulary and expressions through English movies, series, and music (Sockett, 2014). For example, Alsaif and Masrai (2019) did a case study of a male university student in Saudi Arabia, focusing on his extensive reading and vocabulary acquisition. They instructed a participant to read extensively for eight weeks outside the classroom. The participant’s receptive vocabulary was measured before and after the treatment, and results showed that extensive reading contributed to the participant’s vocabulary, suggesting that the participant learned up to eight words from his reading, as compared to two words per hour from language classes where reading texts from a textbook are short and scattered.

Incidental learning can also happen in writing, as learners can pick up the different aspects of a text, such as grammatical features. Aka (2020) studied the effects of incidental learning of one specific grammatical feature through reading. Japanese high school learners in an experimental group read sentences that included infinitives used as nouns, while the control group participants read the same number of reading passages, but with only 10 sentences with to-infinitives as nouns. Pre- and post-test intervention grammar tests showed that the experimental group incidentally

noticed and learned about to-infinitives as nouns through reading. The results suggest that students learn language forms even while focusing on reading comprehension.

Affective filter. According to Krashen's (1982) *Affective Filter hypothesis*, affective variables can influence the success of second language acquisition. For example, when English language learners enjoy learning the second language, their affective filter is lower, facilitating L2 acquisition. With IDLE, learners usually learn and practice English in a low affective filter environment because teachers and classmates are not around. For instance, they can comfortably watch YouTube videos or Netflix in English in the privacy of their homes. The activities may create favorable conditions for English learning, like incidentally acquiring English expressions and vocabulary words.

Moreover, for writing, when students have a high affective filter such as anxiety, they may have lower achievements in writing. Fakeye and Ohia (2016) studied the relationship between writing anxiety and students' achievements in essay writing. Using the Essay Writing Achievement Test and the Writing Anxiety Questionnaire, they found a negative significant relationship between writing anxiety and writing achievement. The results imply that the higher the writing anxiety, the lower the achievement in essay writing. According to Lee (2021), students may go through anxiety in the classroom because of internal factors (e.g., shyness or lack of confidence) or external factors (e.g., test anxiety and fear of being judged by others). IDLE may facilitate vocabulary and writing development in an environment with a low affective filter because there are fewer negative emotions, such as embarrassment or fear (Lewis, 2020) when learners comfortably engage in IDLE activities (e.g., interacting in fun online environments) while incidentally acquiring English (Lee, 2021).

Learner Autonomy. When doing IDLE activities, students have *learner autonomy* (Holec, 1981) because they primarily take charge of their learning, and they choose the materials they want to watch, read, or listen to, and through IDLE, they select their way of learning English. In the case of vocabulary, learners become autonomous and may consciously learn vocabulary outside the classroom due to the limited exposure to English in formal classes. Learner autonomy plays an important role in vocabulary development and enhancement (Haddad, 2016). For writing, learner autonomy can have a positive impact on writing proficiency. Bagheri and Aeen (2011) investigated the impact of practicing autonomy on the writing proficiency of Iranian intermediate EFL learners. They were divided into an autonomous group and a non-autonomous group which followed the traditional approach to writing. Both groups underwent a pre-test and a post-test, and the results revealed that the autonomous group outperformed the non-autonomous group. In contrast to autonomous learning, classroom learning involves students having less freedom to choose because teachers often use a teacher-centered approach and select learning materials such as textbooks.

New Literacies Theory. New literacies, a term coined by David Buckingham (1993), refers to the new forms of literacy that arise from developments in digital technology. According to Lewis (2016), powerful digital technologies and new media, which continuously develop, has changed the way people read, write, and communicate. New media is often associated to information communication technologies (ICTs). The New Literacies Theory posits that each new ICT requires new literacy skills for its effective use. Literacy is not just limited to printed and written texts, but has extended to meaning-making practices using digital technologies (Sang,

2017). For example, the internet needs an increasing skill set involving reading information on websites, writing email messages (Coiro & Dobler, 2007), and posting on social media. Young people spend a significant amount of time online and use multimedia applications on digital devices. These activities produce more new literacies, such as creating and sharing videos.

Considering the aforementioned theories and principles, I conducted this present research to study whether these also apply to the IDLE activities of Filipino SHS students and their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Adolescents' Exposure to IDLE

Research shows that adolescents are highly exposed to digital technologies. In the study conducted by Nagata et al. (2021), adolescents reported a daily screen time of nearly eight hours a day during the pandemic, double the pre-pandemic estimates of four hours a day. This digital media consumption has affected language learning; many learners of English as a second or foreign language independently learn and use English through extramural digital settings (Lee, 2021). Self-directed English learning using digital media (e.g., television, DVDs, YouTube) is a growing trend in Asia (Lee & Sylvén, 2021).

In the Philippines, the use of ICT for language learning was primarily documented in the context of formal instruction (Caipang et al., 2021; Barrot, 2018; Arnobit et al., 2018; Dela Rosa, 2016; Mabuan & Ebron, 2016). Given the Filipino youth's high exposure to the internet and social media (86.8%, according to the Philippine Statistics Authority, 2020), it is plausible that they have also improved their English skills through informal learning. According to the 2019 Functional Literacy,

Education, and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS), Filipinos exposed to different mass media forms (including the internet) registered high functional literacy rates (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2020).

Filipinos have reported practicing the following online activities: (1) watching online videos, as 99.4 percent of Filipino internet users watch online videos as of 2020, especially on YouTube (Statista, 2020); (2) listening to music streaming services which 82.2 percent of Filipino internet users do (Statista, 2020); (3) using social media, since Filipinos spend the most time on social media worldwide, with an average of 4 hours and 15 minutes a day (Chua, 2021); (4) reading ebooks or listening to audiobooks, as the 2017 Readership Survey commissioned by the National Book Development Board (NBDB) revealed that the Filipino youth respondents spend more time on eBooks than other formats with 14.16 hours a month, and spend 12.68 hours listening to audiobooks (compared to reading print books for only 8.70 hours a month), (5) online gaming, since 74 percent of Filipino internet users play mobile games, 65 percent play PC games, and 45 percent play console games (Elliott, 2020), and (6) reading and/or writing on social reading platforms like Wattpad, because the Philippines is one of Wattpad's biggest markets, with millions of Filipino users uploading more than 13 million stories on the platform as of 2019 (Wattpad, 2019). It can be concluded that these online activities are done by a significant percentage of young Filipinos because the proportion of internet users is highest among this age group (Nazario et al., 2019). Since English is the most popular online language, Filipino English learners may probably have also been practicing IDLE; more research still needs to be done in this area.

Studies have positively correlated IDLE activities with different language and literacy learning outcomes, such as speaking, vocabulary, grammar, and English grades. For instance, Lee and Dressman's (2018) research found that the diversity of Korean EFL students' IDLE activities correlated significantly with speaking and productive vocabulary tests and willingness to communicate online. Lai, Zhu, and Gong (2015) studied EFL learners in mainland China, focusing on out-of-class learning of English (e.g., searching the internet for English language materials), which showed a positive relationship with English grades. IDLE has also been positively linked to grammar and scores in standardized English tests (Cole & Vanderplank, 2016; Lee, 2019).

IDLE is also associated with the affective dimensions of second language acquisition. For example, Lee and Drajeti (2019) investigated the relationship between IDLE and affective variables (i.e., grit, motivation, self-confidence, and second language speaking anxiety) among Indonesian EFL university students. Their willingness to communicate in the second language correlated significantly with IDLE activities and affective variables. Likewise, Lai, Zhu, and Gong's (2015) study also associated the out-of-class English learning of Chinese EFL learners with language learning efficacy and enjoyment.

Aside from studies in EFL contexts, IDLE has also been researched in Nordic countries, such as Denmark and Sweden, whose inhabitants have the best non-native English skills in the world, according to the eighth edition of the EF English Proficiency Index (Nikel, 2019). These Scandinavian countries are among the best at English as a second language (The World Economic Forum, 2015). In Denmark, Jensen (2016) conducted a study about how Danish young English language learners' engagement

with Extramural English significantly related to their vocabulary scores. In Sweden, Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015) investigated the relationship between out-of-school digital gameplay and English vocabulary measures and grading outcomes; the results show that the frequent gamers used the most advanced vocabulary and had the highest grades. Similar to Scandinavian countries, the Philippines also has English as a second language, so IDLE can also be investigated in this context.

Aside from bilingual learners, IDLE can also help content area learners, as there are many online courses in English focusing on mathematics, science, and social studies. These courses are readily available online and learners can access whenever and wherever they choose (Dressman, 2019). In the Philippines, English is the primary medium of instruction in schools (Cabigon, 2015), including senior high school and IDLE can help the students' comprehension in the different content areas.

Research about this area of informal language learning is still in its early stage (Lee & Dressman, 2017), but it has shown promising results to different language learning outcomes. The present study focuses on IDLE's relationship to the variables of vocabulary and writing.

Theories of Vocabulary Development

According to Rasinki and Rupley (2019), vocabulary knowledge is needed for reading comprehension and learning, as readers who know the meaning of the words in the text are more likely to understand what they are reading. Proficient readers typically have an extensive vocabulary. Vocabulary is required for "background knowledge, concepts about the world, understanding discipline content, integration of new learning with what is known, and representation of abstract understandings" (p.

ix). Learners' breadth and depth of vocabulary affect their interaction and comprehension of what they read. Aside from reading, a strong vocabulary also improves listening, speaking, and writing (Fujita, 2020).

Theories of vocabulary development relevant to this study include motivation theory (Moody et al., 2018) and incidental vocabulary acquisition (Laufer, 2003, as cited in Zou & Yang, 2019). The motivation theory proposes that readers engage with a text that aligns with their goals, desires, and objectives. Readers are intrinsically driven to read because they are curious about the book's topic or the author, have self-efficacy when reading, and are given freedom of choice of reading material. Vocabulary practices based on this theory include technology-based activities. Motivation theory may be apparent in IDLE, as IDLE learners are intrinsically motivated to learn English because of their interest and enjoyment in learning.

Aside from having the motivation to read texts, learners acquire vocabulary through an extensive exposure to written language, which can be helped by incidental vocabulary acquisition (West, 2017). Incidental vocabulary acquisition refers to learning new words without the intention to do so, but as a by-product of listening and reading (Laufer, 2003, as cited in Zou & Yang, 2019). This kind of learning is done implicitly and subconsciously by being exposed to spoken or written language (West, 2017). Research suggests that vocabulary growth in learners with advanced English proficiency may have been a result of a combination of both formal and informal vocabulary learning. Aside from deliberate, focused study, vocabulary can also be learned incidentally by listening and reading, determining meaning through context clues (Nation, 2013a, 2013b, as cited in Reynolds & Teng, 2021). Studies have demonstrated incidental learning of vocabulary can happen by watching movies in the

target language (Ashcroft, Garner, et al., 2018), watching movies with subtitles (Sadiku, 2017), listening to songs (Pavia, Webb, & Faez, 2019), playing online games (Calvo-Ferrer & Belda-Medina, 2021), and online reading (Teng, 2018). In a study conducted by Niitemaa (2020) about the relationship between online out-of-school exposure and vocabulary among Finnish teenagers, it was found that there was a positive correlation between the time they spent reading online sites and their vocabulary scores.

Research has also shown the effectiveness of extensive reading on incidental vocabulary acquisition in EFL learners (Alsaif & Masrai, 2019). Many English learners seem to be making significant progress in incidental vocabulary learning through informal or extramural English learning through digital means (Sockett, 2014).

As students get older, they need to have a more expansive vocabulary because they are expected to read more complex texts (Ford-Connors, & Paratore, 2015). Many adolescent students have a hard time with vocabulary (Moody, Hu, et al., 2018). This may be evident among Filipino students, who scored lowest in reading comprehension among 79 countries in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (San Juan, 2019). Filipino students also scored just the minimum proficiency in reading and writing in the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019, 60% of whom have “limited vocabulary” (Balinbin, 2020).

Educators and learners face several issues in vocabulary development. First is the large number of words students have to learn to cope with their academic work. The second is that word knowledge is complex; it entails more than simply knowing the dictionary definition. Just memorizing the dictionary definition does not ensure the ability to use a word in reading and writing (Texas Education Agency, 2002). Another

issue is that some teenagers will have difficulty learning new words; those with language and literacy learning problems will have a more challenging time developing vocabulary skills (Spencer, 2016). Also, socioeconomically disadvantaged adolescents tend to have low vocabulary scores (Spencer, Clegg, and Stackhouse 2012).

Research suggests vocabulary is learned through wide reading (Ford-Connors & Paratore, 2015), knowledge of morphologically complex words (Nippold & Sun, 2008), and deriving word meaning from context (Fukkink & Glopper, 1998). Instruction that combines both morphemic and contextual analysis may improve vocabulary knowledge (Baumann, Edwards, et al., 2003). Comprehensive vocabulary development, which focuses on metacognitive word-learning skills, has also been effective for vocabulary achievement (Lublimer & Smetana, 2005). The direct instruction of target words is also helpful in vocabulary development. The teacher can situate the target vocabulary in different instructional activities and events so that students have repeated opportunities to encounter and use the words authentically (Ford-Connors, & Paratore, 2015)

Spencer (2016) likewise recommends giving opportunities for students to extract meanings of words from contexts using clues, repeating the words, and providing opportunities to use them in different contexts. She also suggests discussing the different aspects of a new word by teaching “what it means (semantic), what it sounds like (phonological), how it fits within sentences (grammatical), and how it is written (orthographic).” Moreover, she encourages teaching-learning strategies, such as dictionary skills, clarifying when a word is not understood, and figuring out new words using context.

Vocabulary and Language Learning

Vocabulary learning in a second language (L2) or second language vocabulary acquisition refers to the process of learning vocabulary in another language after the first language. Vocabulary knowledge is essential for second language learners because a limited vocabulary in a second language hinders successful communication (Alqahtani, 2015). “Lexical knowledge is central to communicative competence and to the acquisition of a second language” (Richards, 2000, p. xi). A good vocabulary improves different areas of communication—listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Miller, n.d.). Successful vocabulary acquisition is positively associated to successful reading ability (Dickinson, Flushman, & Freiberg, 2009, as cited in Sa’d & Rajabi, 2018), among other language outcomes.

According to Nation (2001, as cited in Alqahtani, 2015), there is a complementary relationship between vocabulary knowledge and language use: vocabulary knowledge enables language use and language use can lead to more vocabulary knowledge. Learners must have the opportunity to learn new vocabulary through listening and reading activities, and they should also have the chance to improve their vocabulary knowledge through speaking and writing. (Nation, 2013). Acquiring vocabulary is needed for successful second language use and plays a crucial role in the speaking and writing (Nation, 2001; Gu, 2003; Read, 2000; Maximo, 2000, as cited in Alqahtani, 2015). Failure in learning vocabulary may lead to difficulties in language reception and production (Wei, 2007; as cited in Sa’d & Rajabi, 2018).

Measuring Vocabulary

Vocabulary assessment involves the measurement of lexical items. Researchers must choose instruments that validly and accurately describe the aspects of vocabulary being studied (Schmitt, 2010). In this study, the Productive Vocabulary Levels Test was used, which was developed by Laufer and Nation (1999). This was the same test utilized in related studies by Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015), Lee (2017), and Lee and Dressman (2017). It is used to measure controlled vocabulary knowledge, which is the ability to use a word when required to do so. This instrument gives a sentence context or a definition with a clue of the beginning letters of the target words. For example, "The garden was full of fra__ flowers." The test-takers are instructed to supply the predetermined target words. (He, 2019). This test is mainly effective for students with a limited vocabulary size, as it identifies what words the test-takers do not know (Meara & Fitzpatrick, 2000, as cited in He, 2019).

IDLE and Vocabulary Development

Based on the previous discussion, it is evident that an English learner's vocabulary development is not just limited to formal classroom instruction, but can also occur in informal, specifically in digital contexts. In fact, several recent studies associate the informal learning of English with vocabulary outcomes. Three studies (Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019) focused on how digital gameplay had a positive association with English language learners' vocabulary performance.

For instance, Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015) investigated the relationship between out-of-school digital gameplay with English vocabulary measures and grades

in school. In Sweden, where the study was conducted, English is mainstream and can be considered a second language. They collected data from 80 teenage Swedish English as second language learners using questionnaires, language diaries, vocabulary tests, essays, and grades. They used shortened versions of the Productive and Vocabulary Levels Tests (Laufer & Nation, 1995; Nation, 2001). The respondents were divided according to the frequency of gameplay: (1) non-gamers, (2) moderate gamers, who played less than five hours a week, and (3) frequent gamers, who played five hours or more a week. Results showed that the frequent gamers had the highest grades, the highest-rated essays, and used the most advanced vocabulary in the essays. The non-gamers followed them, and the lowest scorers were the non-gamers. Frequent gamers scored the highest in the vocabulary tests. The researchers also found that the non-gamers were predominantly girls, and the frequent gamers were all boys; playing games appears to correlate with the vocabulary test scores and English grades of the boys. Sundqvist and Wikstrom linked this type of language learning to incidental or naturalistic English learning, which refers to the learning of vocabulary without the intention to do so, when the learner's main objective is to do something else, like to communicate (Laufer and Hulstijn, 2001). In the context of this study, the acquisition of English vocabulary may be a by-product of wanting to understand the game or to communicate with the other players.

A similar study was done in Denmark by Jensen (2016) about young English language learners' contact with and use of English outside the classroom. These students received little English instruction formally. Data was collected using a language diary. The researcher found that the respondents were exposed to English through gaming, listening to music, reading, talking, watching television, and writing.

Using the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, the researcher gathered their vocabulary proficiency scores. The respondents spent the most time on digital gaming, listening to music, and watching television. Boys engaged significantly more in gaming than girls. The results also showed that gaming with both oral and written English input and gaming with only written English were significantly associated with vocabulary scores of boys. The results of this study are similar to that of Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015) because both found that boys did more gaming than girls, and that their gaming activity was correlated with their vocabulary outcomes.

Sundqvist (2019) published another study relating the digital gaming of Swedish teenagers to English vocabulary. It examined the relation between playing “commercial-off-the-shelf games in the wild” and English vocabulary, and compared the results to non-gamers’ vocabulary. The term “in the wild” describes informal language learning that happens outside the classroom, such as in a digital setting. Data was gathered with a mixed-methods approach using questionnaires, English grades, productive and receptive vocabulary tests, interviews, and essays. The Productive Vocabulary Levels Test by Laufer and Nation (1999) and the Vocabulary Levels Test by Nation (2001) were both used, which were used in the studies previously mentioned. Results demonstrated that the time of gameplay was significantly positively correlated with test scores. Sundqvist noted that when learners invest time in gaming, incidental vocabulary learning happens. The gamers had significantly higher vocabulary scores than the non-gamers, and used advanced or infrequent words in essays. The results of this study imply that commercial-off-the-shelf games matter for the vocabulary development of English language learners.

While some studies focused exclusively on one IDLE activity (digital gameplay) and its correlation with vocabulary outcomes, other researchers included other types of IDLE activities, such as watching movies, reading blogs, and communicating on social media (Huang, 2016; Lee, 2017; Lee & Dressman, 2018; Arndt & Woore, 2018; Lee, 2019; Niitemaa, 2020; Mohammed and Ali; 2021).

For example, Lee (2017) included different IDLE activities (e.g., using social media and watching YouTube videos) in his study. He explored how quantity (frequency/amount of time) and quality (diversity) of Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) activities were associated with second language vocabulary outcomes of Korean EFL university students. He gathered quantitative and qualitative data through a questionnaire, an interview, and two vocabulary tests, the Productive Vocabulary Levels Test (PVLТ) by Laufer and Nation (1999—the same test used by Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015), and the Receptive Vocabulary Levels Test (RVLT) by Nation (1990). The questionnaire asked about the quantity of the respondents' IDLE activities, using the question: "On average, how many hours each day did you spend engaging in IDLE activities outside the classroom in the past 6 months?" The PVLТ was used to measure students' productive ability, namely by assessing if they use a word correctly. The RVLT measured receptive vocabulary ability by assessing the students' understanding of the word. Lee used these two vocabulary measures to have a more comprehensive understanding of the students' vocabulary knowledge. This study showed that the participants practiced different types of IDLE activities, with the most respondents reporting that they (1) watch documentary, drama, movie, and talk-shows, and (2) use social media. The study also revealed that the quantity of IDLE was not associated with vocabulary scores, unlike what the results of earlier research

suggested. In terms of the quality of IDLE, respondents engaged in both form-focused and meaning-focused IDLE activities. A form-focused IDLE activity involves the student learning the accuracy of linguistic forms using digital tools (e.g., using Google Translate to translate English to Korean or looking up an English word using a dictionary). A meaning-focused IDLE activity involves the students “focusing more on the fluency of authentic language use in unstructured, naturalistic digital settings (e.g., playing a multiplayer online game in English, or chatting via social media with other English users)” (p. 5). The study found that the quality of IDLE activities, which combined both form-focused and meaning-focused language learning, is needed for the learners’ vocabulary acquisition. The conclusion was that the frequency of IDLE activities does not automatically lead to successful vocabulary learning.

Like the previous study, Lee and Dressman (2018) also investigated the quality of IDLE activities, relating it to different English learning outcomes of Korean university students. Like Lee’s (2017) study, the researchers defined IDLE quality by classifying them into form-focused and meaning-focused IDLE activities. They collected data from Korean EFL university students through a demographic survey and three assessment measures: (1) willingness to communicate online, (2) a vocabulary levels test in English, and (3) speaking scores. The Productive Vocabulary Levels Test (PVLTL) by Laufer and Nation (1999) was used, which is the same assessment used by Lee (2017) and Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015). The results showed that diverse IDLE activities, including form-focused and meaning-focused language learning, were significantly related to English speaking proficiency, greater willingness to communicate online, and higher productive vocabulary scores. This study had similar findings with Lee (2017), as they both associated the quality of IDLE with vocabulary

outcomes. In this study, the researcher described the case of one of their participants, Su-ja (not her real name), who was born and raised in Korea, and through a variety of IDLE activities, learned English and scored high in English proficiency assessments. The English version of *World of Warcraft*, in particular, is where she had a massive exposure to oral and written English. Watching English movies and dramas helped her incidentally to acquire a large vocabulary, including colloquial expressions. This finding is consistent with the discussion that incidental vocabulary learning can lead to vocabulary growth through listening and reading (Reynolds & Teng, 2021).

While Lee (2017) and Lee and Dressman (2018) focused on IDLE activities as a whole, Arndt and Woore (2018) focused on engagement with two different online media in English: written blog posts and YouTube vlogs, using the theoretical construct *informal second language learning*. They compared the English vocabulary acquisition from these activities. With an experimental approach, they gathered data from EFL learners from different backgrounds (e.g., German and Dutch). They adapted Webb's (2007) tests, as well as the Vocabulary Levels Test, to measure different aspects of vocabulary knowledge (i.e., orthography, semantics, and grammatical function) were tested using the Vocabulary Levels Test. The results showed that incidental vocabulary learning in almost equal amounts happened from both watching vlogs and reading blog posts. The written blog posts seemed to have led to greater gains in vocabulary knowledge, while the videos promoted greater recall of the grammatical functions of target words and greater recognition and recall of their meanings.

Lee (2019) extended the inquiry about this topic by investigating the relationship of quantity and diversity of IDLE practices and different English learning outcomes. He gathered data from Korean EFL university students through a questionnaire, six

English learning outcomes, and interviews. The questionnaire asked about the students' demographic information, English learning outcomes, and the quantity of IDLE activities. The English learning outcomes included (1) the psychological aspects of English levels (i.e., Confidence, Enjoyment, and Anxiety), (2) the standardized English ability (TOEIC Score), and (3) the productive language outcomes of speaking and vocabulary. The Productive Vocabulary Levels test (PVLТ) by Laufer and Nation (1999) was used to determine students' vocabulary outcomes, which was also used by Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015), Lee (2017), and Lee and Dressman (2017). The results revealed that IDLE quantity, age, and major significantly predicted confidence and enjoyment. However, the quantity of IDLE was not positively associated with the Speaking or PVLТ score. This study is similar to Lee's study in 2017, as both studies found that the IDLE quantity was not associated with vocabulary outcomes. The findings of both studies are not consistent with earlier related research, like that of Sundqvist and Wikstrom (2015) and Jensen (2016), which both found a correlation between the quantity of IDLE (i.e., digital gameplay) and vocabulary scores. Most of the previous research on the subject was done in the Nordic countries, so IDLE quantity may result in different learning outcomes in other contexts, like that of Korea, where Lee's (2019) research is located.

Aside from vocabulary knowledge, IDLE activities seem to have influenced the use of second language vocabulary in writing. Huang (2016) did a study in Sweden when she investigated extramural English of upper secondary students in Sweden and their attitude toward learning English from EE activities and in-class settings. The results, gathered through questionnaires, revealed that the students are regularly exposed to extramural English, especially social media, music, TV/films, YouTube,

and video games. They are generally positive about how they acquire and learn English. A noteworthy response from a student was, *“I learned a lot from playing games, sometimes when we are writing essays, words that I never used before pops up.”* This comment may be related to the concept of incidental vocabulary acquisition with effects on writing because he may have unintentionally learned a new word and used it.

Niitemaa (2020) examined Finnish upper secondary school learners' out-of-school activities in relation to their receptive English vocabulary knowledge across high-, mid-, and low-frequency levels. She collected data from 46 students aged 16-17 using a questionnaire asking for the type and frequency of online activities outside school, as well as the extent of their English exposure. These activities included online reading, playing computer games, watching films, videos, series, and streaming services, listening to English music, and communicating on social network sites. The participants were also asked to evaluate their vocabulary acquisition through out-of-school word learning by choosing one from the following choices: *A lot of words, Certainly some words, Perhaps some words or I don't know*. The participants also had an option to give examples of words they remembered having learned. Receptive vocabulary was examined using the Vocabulary Levels Test (Schmitt, Schmitt & Clapham, 2001; Nation, 1983), which measured recognition of high-, mid-, and low-frequency level words. Statistical analysis, namely Pearson's r , simple linear and stepwise regression, was used to relate online out-of-school activities and recognition of English words at high-, mid-, and low-frequency levels. The results showed that about half of the students were in contact with English content daily through music, films, sites, and games. They had daily exposure to English music and films, and less

than half exposure to English sites and games. In contrast, they had less daily exposure to English social media. The participants believed that they learned English words and phrases through out-of-school online activities, and they were able to share examples of the learned words. The correlations between out-of-school English activities and vocabulary scores revealed that listening to English music daily had a positive correlation with low-frequency vocabulary. Watching English films and reading English websites had positive and significant correlations with vocabulary scores when the learners had daily contact with all-English content. Gaming had a stronger correlation with vocabulary scores compared to other activities.

Peters (2018) investigated how Flemish EFL learners are exposed to English language media outside the classroom, and whether this out-of-class exposure to English language media is related to their vocabulary knowledge. She administered a vocabulary test and questionnaire to the participants. The results show that the participants are frequently exposed to English language media, and that there is a positive relationship between the learners' vocabulary knowledge to TV programs and movies and the internet. The highest correlation was found between vocabulary knowledge and browsing English language websites.

The studies above in this section indicate that IDLE generally has a positive relationship with vocabulary outcomes, but the findings differ in language learning contexts. IDLE quantity appears to be positively correlated with vocabulary scores in the European context (Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016). In the Korean context, however, the quality of IDLE activities (a combination of form-focused and meaning-focused language learning) has a stronger correlation with vocabulary scores (Lee, 2019). The Productive Vocabulary Levels Test was also used in most of

the studies mentioned because it is one of the most validated and reliable vocabulary tests (Lee, 2019). Lastly, the researchers also noted the presence of incidental vocabulary learning in IDLE activities in the studies (Lee & Dressman, 2017).

Theories of Writing Development

In addition to vocabulary, writing is another essential skill that adolescent English language learners need to have, and according to recent research, IDLE may improve that. According to the National Institute for Literacy (2007), writing is the ability to produce text to communicate for different purposes and audiences effectively. It is a tool for communication and learning that allows the writer to document, collect, and pass on information. It is also a means of expression and persuasion. In addition, improving one's writing skills can help one's capacity to learn.

Several skills are involved in writing, such as grammar and spelling (National Institute for Literacy, 2007). Moreover, vocabulary and reading skills are necessary to create meaningful text. Learners also need the skills of sentence construction, grammar, and punctuation to write (Lee, 2021). Writers need to learn to be self-directed and goal-oriented and to use self-regulation strategies (e.g., goal-setting, self-instruction, self-monitoring) to independently plan, organize and revise their work. They should also learn to write using different text genres like narrative, persuasive, and descriptive essays (National Institute for Literacy, 2007).

Writing theories that are pertinent to this study are the sociocultural theory and self-efficacy beliefs and motivation in writing development. According to sociocultural theory, the students' learning of writing is influenced by their social and cultural context (Mohammadzadeh et al., 2020). Writing is seen as a social act and social contexts

affect the way authors write and the content of their writing. Writing is influenced by social relationships and communities (Slavkov, 2015). This theory is apparent in IDLE because learners have many opportunities to write for audiences, like writing fanfiction (Zheng & Lin, 2020), or joining writing communities on Wattpad (Korobkova & Black, 2014).

Secondly, writing self-efficacy refers to the learner's judgment of how well they can accomplish a writing task based on their self-assessments of grammar usage, composition, and mechanical skills (Pajares & Valiente, 2001, as cited in Sun & Wang, 2020). Writing self-efficacy may be apparent in IDLE, because learners have to have confidence in their own writing skills when posting or publishing for a wider audience online (Bippert, 2017). Thirdly, writing motivation refers to the learner's inclination, interest, and energy in writing (Martin et al., 2016). This theory may be related to IDLE because learners are intrinsically motivated to write, publish and post online because of their interest and enjoyment in learning (Bippert, 2017; Lee, 2021).

Furthermore, writing is so important that those who do not learn it well are academically and occupationally disadvantaged (Graham, 2019). Evidence has shown that not all students have been taught to become competent writers. Graham and Rijlaarsdam (2016) presented issues in writing instruction from countries like the United States, Belgium, China, Macao, Taiwan, Portugal, and Brazil. In some countries, the time teachers spent teaching writing was insufficient, and teachers were not adequately prepared to teach writing. Graham (2018) mentioned that biological, environmental, genetic, and environmental factors might influence a learner's writing skills. He cited poverty in particular, which can impede writing development due to a lack of writing and reading materials available at home, a lack of competent teachers,

and the other factors of low-quality housing, lack of medical care, poor nutrition that all influence cognitive development (Parrett and Budge, 2016). Many students do not get the writing instruction they deserve or need (Graham, 2018). In the Philippine context, a report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2020) stated that senior high school students “cannot even correctly construct basic sentences in English” (p. 6). This difficulty was especially evident in research subjects.

Like vocabulary, writing can also be associated with extensive reading. Extensive reading is the term used to describe learners reading texts for enjoyment. For extensive reading to happen, a student should read a large amount of text, that there should be a variety of material to choose from, and that the material should be easy and enjoyable to read (Robb, 2018). In other words, students learn to read by actually reading instead of scrutinizing the vocabulary, grammar, and phrases. Extensive reading is also done online (Bui & Macalister, 2021) and informally (Ewert, 2019). Through extensive reading, learners learn skills necessary for writing, like vocabulary (Ewert, 2019) and grammar (Johansson, 2014). Extensive reading has been found to positively connect with EFL learners' writing fluency (Fitriansyah & Miftah, 2020). Extensive reading may therefore be involved in how IDLE influences writing skills.

Writing skills may also be developed by digital writing in informal settings. According to Zheng and Lin (2020), many language learners are engaged in technology-facilitated writing outside the classroom, such as blogging, tweeting, messaging, and online gaming. These activities may benefit second language writing by (1) helping students develop their identities as writers, (2) reinforcing audience and

authorship awareness, (3) improving motivation and autonomy in writing, and (3) encouraging interaction and exchange of feedback between readers and writers.

Writing and Language Learning

Writing is an important skill that involves the process of thinking, drafting, and revising. It requires the person to learn what and how to write, and how to apply grammatical rules (Pongsukvajchakul, 2021). It is a complex process in which the writer has to be aware of and combine different components of language successfully (Abrams, 2010). As learners become proficient in their second language, they become better at writing, are able to produce more effective texts and attend more fully to aspects of their writing (Cumming, 1989). A learner's capability for a language is reinforced when they express their thoughts and ideas through writing (Xia, 2011 as cited in Pongsukvajchakul, 2021).

According to Godwin-Jones (2022), learning to write in a second language is a challenging aspect of second language acquisition. The second language learner will have to learn a new writing system, grammatical knowledge, and vocabulary in the target language. For learners to be considered basically literate, they will have to achieve minimally functional reading and writing ability in the second language. In the present communicative environment, these skills are needed to communicate through digital networks.

The Reading and Writing Connection

Writing is closely connected with reading; they are two connected parts of the same whole. Reading can be considered as the active process of making new

meanings and new knowledge, and writing is based upon or influenced by ideas, theories or stories that come from reading (Kashyap & Dyquisto, 2020). Moreover, reading exposes one to different writing styles, helps one to subconsciously learn syntax, grammar, style, punctuation, generic conventions, structure, and document design (Petelin, 2021). A study showed that reading for pleasure has a positive impact on writing achievement, and that it helps learners find inspiration, expand their vocabulary, and improve their grammar (Attiyat, 2019). A meta-analysis by Graham et al. (2017) found that teaching reading improved writing, with statistically significant effects on the overall measure of writing, specific measures of writing quality, words written, and spelling. It was also found that when students read text, this improved their writing performance, yielding statistically significant impact on overall measure of writing, specific measures of writing quality, and spelling.

On the other hand, writing can also make learners better readers. When students are taught how to write complex sentences and different kinds of texts, they learn how to read and comprehend a wider variety of writing (Schwartz, 2023). A meta-analysis by Graham and Hebert (2011) found that when students write about the material they read, writing improves their reading comprehension, reading fluency, and word reading. Moreover, they found that increasing how much students write improves their reading comprehension.

These previous literatures show the reciprocal nature of reading and writing, and that each skill can improve the other.

The Writing Process

According to Caulfield (2023), the writing process has five basic parts: (1) prewriting, which involves choosing a topic, narrowing it down, and researching for the needed information; (2) planning and outlining, which refers to making a structure before writing; (3) writing the first draft; (4) redrafting and revising, in which the writer looks critically at the first draft and finds room for improvement; and (5) editing and proofreading for clarity, grammar, sentence structure, and typographical errors. In this study, the students are instructed to follow the essential steps of the writing process, which is to plan, write, and revise their essays in 40 minutes.

Measuring Writing

Assessment of student writing involves rendering a judgment about the quality of student work. According to Behizadeh and Engelhard Jr. (2011), here are two research traditions to classify the theories of the measurement of writing, test-score and scaling. As its name implies, the test-score tradition emphasizes test scores with a primary concern of measuring errors, and the breakdown of an observed test score into different components including a true score with various error components. On the other hand, scaling theory is used to make rating scales for assessing writing. It involves developing an instrument that combines qualitative constructs and quantitative metric units (Trochim, n.d.). Rating scales are tools to score writing performances efficiently, systematically, and transparently (Baker & Turner, 2022).

Assessing writing typically involves the use of rubrics, which are tools to evaluate and classify writing. These are charts or grids that identify the central requirements or goals of a writing task. Evaluators assess whether, and how

effectively, the learners meet the criteria. Rubrics categorize what is being evaluated in the written work and have “descriptors” for evaluation (University of Nebraska-Lincoln, n.d.). In this study, the following descriptors were used (Kwantlen Polytechnic University, n.d.; Read Write Think, 2013):

Focus. The essay is focused, purposeful, and reflects clear insight and ideas.

Support. The author persuasively supports the main point with well-developed reasons and/or examples.

Organization. The author effectively organizes ideas to build a logical, coherent essay.

Word Choice. The author uses vivid words and phrases. The choice and placement of words seems accurate, natural, and not forced.

Sentence Structure, Grammar, Mechanics, & Spelling. All sentences are well constructed and have varied structure and length. The author makes no errors in grammar, mechanics, and/or spelling.

IDLE and Writing Development

The following studies show that the development of an English language learner’s writing is not just limited to formal instruction, but can also happen in informal, digital contexts (Olsson, 2016; Sundqvist & Wikstrom's study, 2015; Sauro, 2020; Shafirova & Cassany, 2019). There have been no studies published about the relationship between writing skills and the concept of IDLE per se, but related studies have examined the variables.

First, Olsson (2016) discussed three studies she had conducted in Sweden to investigate the impact of extramural English (EE) and content and language integrated

learning (CLIL), where school subjects are taught in English. Under the construct of EE, she included online computer games, reading online materials, and other Internet activities. In one study, she investigated the impact of EE on Grade 9 (16 years old) students' writing proficiency, and whether there were differences in two different text types (i.e., letters and newspaper articles) between groups of students with different frequencies of exposure to extramural English. The researcher collected different text types from the Grade 9 students, a letter, and a newspaper article. These were analyzed to see if extramural English affected their register variation, that is, to see if the students' use of language differed between the two text types. The compositions were analyzed using mainly corpus-based methods, focusing on linguistic features and vocabulary. In particular, Olsson analyzed text length, sentence length, word length, and variation of vocabulary. The use of longer words and sentences and a varied vocabulary may be evidence of higher writing proficiency. She also used a background survey that included questions of the frequency of students' use of EE and a language diary where the students recorded how long they had been engaged in EE activities. The results showed that students with greater exposure to EE wrote longer sentences and had more vocabulary variation than those with infrequent use of EE when writing the letter. Moreover, the students with greater exposure to EE used longer and more infrequent words in their articles than in their letters. The results indicate that this group is more capable of register variation than students with infrequent use of EE.

Olsson's results were similar to Sundqvist and Wikstrom's study (2015). They examined the relationship between out-of-school digital gameplay and in-school English vocabulary and grading outcomes of Swedish English learners. Aside from

administering vocabulary tests, they collected data from essays that were part of a Swedish national test in English. These essays were graded by the participants' English teacher, who followed the grading instructions/guidelines of the national agency for education. These essays were also analyzed, and advanced vocabulary was assessed through the frequency of polysyllabic words (words with three or more syllables). Students who were frequent gamers had the highest grades in their essays and had the most advanced vocabulary compared to non-gamers and moderate gamers.

Aside from studies relating informal language learning with writing skills, there is also literature in the field about digital writing in informal settings and how these affect writing skills. For example, Sauro (2020) discussed fan fiction, which are stories found online that "reimagine or reinterpret existing stories, characters and universes found in other texts and media" (p.148). Learners can informally practice writing and develop their writing skills through fan fiction. Fan fiction writers can receive feedback from other users on fanfiction websites on grammar, plot, and characterization. They receive informal mentoring from other fanfiction community members that help develop their writing skills (Evans, Davis, et al., 2017). By writing fan fiction, English language learners develop motivation and confidence in their writing abilities when they write for a wider audience online (Bippert, 2017).

A popular source of fanfiction is Wattpad, an online social reading platform that has user-generated stories such as novels, fanfiction, humor, and poetry (Pianzola, et al. 2020). The Philippines is one of Wattpad's biggest markets with millions of Filipino Wattpad users uploading more than 13 million stories on the platform as of 2019. Many Wattpad stories have been adapted into books, TV shows, and films (Wattpad, 2019).

Korobkova and Black (2014) interviewed international fans of the British musical group One Direction in an online fanfiction Wattpad community. The participants developed writing and editing skills through the fan fiction and found that they developed writing and editing skills through the fanfiction community. One participant claimed that the grammar, vocabulary, and writing efficacy she developed in the community influenced her classroom literacy practices. The participants had engaged in peer editing and giving feedback to one another and their identities are not revealed to one another. Fanfiction writing also helped her spot her mistakes in composition. Suhaeni (2022) had similar findings when they interviewed 23 Wattpad active users; the results showed that the participants claimed through Wattpad, they can share and receive tips about writing. They can also encourage other users to improve their writing. Moreover, Wattpad provides the tools for users to comment and criticize a work directly.

Shafirova and Cassany (2019) also examined fan writing practices in English of an international community of adult fans of the animated cartoon *My Little Pony*. The researchers studied how two groups of fans—one in Russia and the other in Spain—carried out fan practices in English. Using digital ethnography, they gathered data from six adult fans through semi-structured interviews and participant observations over six months. One of the practices they did was to write fanfiction collaboratively. Using Google Docs or Etherpad, the participants worked together on the drafts, and native speakers would check the text for grammar, punctuation, and language flow. The participants would use dictionaries and translators to improve their written English. The researchers noted an exceptional Russian participant, Shor, who claims to have gained 70% of his mastery of English through writing. He would craft pony figurines, sell his figurines online on DeviantArt, and learn English in the process of

communicating with his customers. He made use of Google Translate to translate his messages from Russian to English, but also manually checked and made corrections on the output. The researchers observed that his public messages and comments on DeviantArt had evolved from March 2016 to May 2017. Initially, the contents of his posts were simple descriptive labels for images of his figurines, but as time passed the texts became more fully structured and emotionally engaging. The researchers also found that he improved his grammatical competence. The study showed that digital technology was associated with improved English writing.

The studies in this section show that learning English through digital activities (playing digital games, reading online content, writing fanfiction) has a positive relationship with writing performance. This was evident in the lengths of the texts, sentences, and words, and the variation and the difficulty level of vocabulary (Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015; Olsson, 2016). Some studies suggest how writing fanfiction and learning from fan communities has helped second language learners' grammar, vocabulary, and writing efficacy (Korobkova & Black, 2014; Shafirova & Cassany, 2019). These results can be explained by how extensive reading online may influence writing (Ewert, 2019; Fitriansyah & Miftah, 2020; Bui & Macalister, 2021), and that learners encounter the English language more frequently through digital activities, priming their language acquisition mechanism to compose it into writing (Donaghy, 2016).

Synthesis

The presented literature shows that because of the internet and other digital technologies, language learners have many opportunities to learn English informally.

Ju Seong Lee (2017) called this phenomenon Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE), which is theoretically underpinned by *incidental learning* (Hulstijn, 2013), *learner autonomy* (Holec, 1981), the *Affective Filter hypothesis* (Krashen, 1982);

The increase in vocabulary performance in informal digital settings can be attributed to incidental vocabulary acquisition (Laufer, 2003, as cited in Zou & Yang, 2019) and extensive reading (Alsaif & Masrai, 2019). Substantial research has demonstrated a generally positive relationship between English vocabulary outcomes and digital gameplay (Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019), and IDLE activities in general, such as social media, watching videos, listening to music, and reading online content (Huang, 2016; Lee, 2017; Lee & Dressman, 2017; Arndt & Woore 2018; Lee, 2019; Niitemaa, 2020; Mohammed & Ali, 2021). IDLE is also associated with writing skills because reading for pleasure may improve writing performance (Attiyat, 2019). Other studies suggest that IDLE has a positive relationship with the learners' use of advanced vocabulary in their writing (Olsson, 2016; Sundqvist & Wikstrom, 2015), writing in longer sentences, and using varied registers in different types of texts (Olson, 2016). Writing fanfiction has also helped English language learners' writing because they receive feedback from other members of the fanfiction community while developing grammar, vocabulary, and writing efficacy. (Korobkova & Black, 2014; Shafirova & Cassany, 2019).

The present study attempts to advance the inquiry in an English as a Second Language (ESL) context, the Philippines, where no studies about IDLE have been published so far.

Conceptual Framework

This study aims to investigate (1) what Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) activities Filipino senior high school students are engaged in, (2) the relationship between the participants' time spent on (IDLE) activities and their vocabulary performance and writing performance, and (3) the possible connection of IDLE activities and the participants' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. IDLE is theoretically underpinned by the (1) *incidental language learning* (Hulstijn, 2013, p. 1), as the time spent on IDLE may affect the learners' immersion in English digital or online content, as well as their incidental learning of vocabulary (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019) and writing; (2) the *Affective Filter hypothesis* (Krashen, 1982), as the time learners spend leisurely learning English through IDLE in low affective filter environments may affect how they learn vocabulary and writing, (3) *learner autonomy* (Holec, 1981) as learners take charge of their own learning during their leisure time as they choose what digital materials to watch, read, and listen to, and how to learn English skills with these, including their vocabulary and writing skills, and (4) *new literacies* (Buckingham, 1993), as the learners develop new literacy skills as they engage in digital technologies.

Previous research has demonstrated IDLE's relationship with vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The present study is a mixed methods research, so the quantitative phase of the study focused on the time spent on IDLE (independent variable) and its relationship with vocabulary knowledge and writing skills (dependent variables). In the qualitative phase of the study, I investigated *how* IDLE (independent variable) affects vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The relationships of these variables are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework

The independent variable IDLE is connected using a line to another independent variable that is an aspect of IDLE, which is the time spent on IDLE activities. The effects of IDLE may be influenced by the time spent on these kinds of activities. One-directional arrows were used starting from the independent variables, and pointing towards the dependent variables, vocabulary knowledge and writing skills separately to indicate (1) how IDLE affects the dependent variables (2) how time spent on IDLE may have a correlation with the dependent variables. It had been predicted that there would be a positive relationship between time spent on IDLE and vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, and that IDLE would have a positive effect on these variables as well.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the time Filipino senior high school students spend on IDLE activities and their vocabulary performance.
2. There is no significant relationship between the time Filipino senior high school students spend on IDLE activities and their writing performance.

Expected Outcomes

The qualitative phase of the study is expected to yield new insights about how IDLE influences (positively and/or negatively) vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The outcomes of this study may benefit teachers, parents, and students, as it explores how IDLE influences language and literacy learning.

Operational Definitions of Terms

The following terms have been defined operationally to clarify their use in the study.

Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) refers to the self-directed and informal learning of English using digital devices and online resources, independent of formal learning (Lee & Dressman, 2018). In this research, IDLE activities include (1) watching online videos, (2) listening to English music, (3) using social media, (4) reading digital content, (5) online gaming, (6) reading and/or writing on social reading platforms like Wattpad.

Grade 12 Senior High School Students refer to students who are in their last year of the K to 12 Basic Education program (GovPH, n.d.). They can be in different tracks and strands. In this study, this term applies to Grade 12 students at a private school in Bacolod City. They are in the strands of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy, Business and Management Strand (ABM), and Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS).

Vocabulary refers to the knowledge of words, which include their spellings (orthography), meanings (semantics), and use (grammar) (Ardnt & Woore, 2018; Department of Education and Training Victoria, 2021). This study explores *productive*

vocabulary, which is defined by the words a person regularly uses to express oneself, in speech or in writing (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d.; Benjamin & Crow, 2013). Productive vocabulary was measured using the Productive Vocabulary Levels test (PVLTL) developed by Laufer and Nation (1999).

Writing is the act of composing a text, a skill that needs knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, spelling, sentence construction (National Institute for Literacy, 2007; Laufer, 2013; Nordquist, 2019; Lee, 2021). In this study, a writing test was administered and was measured by focus, support, organization, word choice, sentence structure, grammar, mechanics, and spelling (Kwantlen Polytechnic University, n.d.; Read Write Think, 2013).

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, I discuss the research methods used in this study. I justify the research design used and I describe the participants, the criteria for their inclusion in the study, and how they were sampled. I also explain the research locale and the research instruments. Moreover, in this section, I describe the procedures followed to collect data, including the ethical considerations. Lastly, I discuss the procedure used to analyze the data.

Research Design

In this study, I used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods approach. In this approach, I gathered quantitative data during the first phase, analyzed the results, and then used the results to plan the second, qualitative phase. Participants for the second phase were purposefully selected based on the results of the quantitative phase. The purpose of this design is to have the qualitative data explain the quantitative results in more detail (Creswell, 2014).

The first research question of this study asked about what IDLE activities Filipino senior high school students are engaged in, while the second asked about the correlation between the time Filipino senior high school students spend on IDLE activities and their vocabulary performance and writing performance. The last question asked about how IDLE activities affect their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The qualitative data about how IDLE activities affect the students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills explains the quantitative results about the correlation

between the time they spend on IDLE and (1) their vocabulary performance and (2) writing performance.

The first phase provided quantitative data for the first two research questions. A descriptive research design was used to answer the first question, which asks about *what* IDLE activities the participants are engaged in. Descriptive research was appropriate for this objective because it identifies the number of hours of the participants' practice of each IDLE category. To answer the second question, I used a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between the independent variable (the students' IDLE activities) and the dependent variables (their vocabulary and writing performance).

After the data of the first phase was gathered, the third research question was further investigated by selecting cases among the students. This design was employed to interpret the data of the previous phase. Based on the quantitative results, 20 student participants and their family members were purposefully selected and interviewed about the students' experiences with Informal Digital Learning of English and how this has affected their learning of English.

A mixed methods research design is appropriate because it ensures triangulation of data (George, 2021); results were collected from multiple sources including surveys, tests, and interviews.

Research Participants

Quantitative Phase

Students. The quantitative data were collected from Hiligaynon-speaking Grade 11 and 12 senior high school students in Bacolod City, who are 17-18 years old. This population is appropriate for this study because according to the Pew
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Development of Filipino Senior High School Students 60

Research Center (2020), 94% of 18- to 29-year-olds in the Philippines use the internet, at least occasionally, or own a smartphone. Furthermore, according to the DepEd Learner Information System of the school, all the Grades 11 and 12 students have televisions, cellphones, radios and desktops/laptops. All of them also are able to connect to the internet via mobile data and broadband.

The respondents were selected through stratified random sampling by dividing the population into strata (Hayes, 2021). Data was collected from a sample ($n = 99$) from a population of Grade 11 and 12 students ($N = 139$) from a private school in Bacolod City.

Table 1
Participants' Grades and Sex Assigned at Birth

Sex Assigned at Birth	Number of Participants
Grade 11	
Female	20
Male	33
Total	53
Grade 12	
Female	20
Male	26
Total	46

Most of the students come from middle- or upper-income families and therefore have more possibilities of owning gadgets and having an internet connection (Aldama, 2020).

Qualitative Phase

Students. For the qualitative phase, I used purposive sampling to select a total of 20 students for interviews, based on their performance in the quantitative phase: 10 male participants (five Grade 11 and five Grade 12) and 10 female participants (five Grade 11 and five Grade 12). They were selected because they reported high amounts of time on IDLE activities daily (11-31 hours), and yielded satisfactory scores in the vocabulary test (11-17 points out of a total of 20) and in the essay test (15-19.33 points out of a total of 20) compared to the rest of the participants. The reason for these criteria is that previous research has shown that more time spent on IDLE activities is related to higher vocabulary knowledge and writing skills (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Olsson, 2016; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019). One of the female participants initially chosen refused to be interviewed, so she had to be replaced with another participant who had slightly lower scores.

Family Members. Information about the students' IDLE activities and the influence of these on vocabulary knowledge and writing skills was also gathered from the participants' family members to collect data from multiple sources (George, 2021). Initially, I tried to contact the parents of the 20 participants because they play an important role in the language and literacy learning of their children (Tamis-LeMonda & Rodriguez, 2009), and it is usually because of them that their children get to own gadgets, like cellphones and iPads (Pinola, 2017). However, several parents were not

available for interviews for various reasons, so I interviewed siblings and a cousin of some of the participants. The criterion for selecting these other family members is that they grew up with the participants and were able to witness their IDLE activities.

Table 2
Family Members of the Participants

Family Member	Number of Participants
Mother	9
Sister	5
Brother	3
Father	2
Cousin	1
TOTAL	20

Research Locale

The study was conducted at a private school in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental, which offers pre-elementary, elementary, junior high school, and senior high school programs. Students from middle- to upper-income families comprise the population. According to the DepEd Learner Information System of the school, all the Grades 11 and 12 students have televisions, cellphones, radios and desktops/laptops. All of them also can connect to the internet via mobile data and broadband.

Research Instruments

For the first phase, to answer the first and second research questions, I used a survey questionnaire, a productive vocabulary levels test, and a writing test. To answer the first and third research question in the second phase, I used a semi-structured interview protocol.

Quantitative Phase

Questionnaire for Students. The purpose of the first questionnaire (see Appendix C) was to collect the students' demographic information, to establish the IDLE activities the participants engage in and the daily time they spend on these activities. Adapting by Niitemaa's (2020) methods and instrument, the students were instructed to report how much time daily they do the following out-of-school activities in English during their free time: (1) watching online films, videos, series, and streaming services (*Videos*); (2) communicating on social networking sites (*Social Networks*); (3) listening to music with English lyrics (*Music*); (4) playing mobile, online, PC, console games, or other digital games (*Digital Gaming*); (5) reading digital content from websites or eBooks (*Reading*) and (6) reading and/or writing on social reading platforms like Wattpad (*Social Reading Platforms*). Examples for each category were given. The students were also asked to enumerate other online and/or digital activities in English (e.g., listening to English podcasts, voice calls on Discord). They were asked to estimate how many hours daily they spend doing each activity in English during their free time. The questionnaire was written in English, had 13 items, was validated by three teachers with Master's degrees, and was pilot tested on eight students. Then, it was administered via Google Forms.

I computed the mean and standard deviation for each preselected IDLE activity: (1) Video, (2) Social Media, (3) Music, (4) Digital Gaming, (5) Reading, (6) Social Reading Platforms, and (7) Other IDLE activities. The mean and the standard deviation were used to summarize the typical value of hours spent daily for each IDLE activity. To determine the total time spent daily on IDLE activities, I calculated the sum of the hours spent for all the activities for each participant.

Productive Vocabulary Levels Test. To measure the students' vocabulary performance, I used the Productive Vocabulary Levels Test (PVLTL; see Appendix D) developed by Laufer and Nation (1999). The PVLTL has been used in related studies (Lee, 2017; Lee & Dressman, 2018; Sundqvist, 2019; Lee, 2019). This is one of the reliable and validated vocabulary tests (Lee, 2019). The PVLTL asks the participant to complete each sentence with the correct word by filling in the blank that already has a few initial letters—e.g., “The garden was full of fra_____ flowers.” (Laufer, & Nation, 1999).

The original Productive Vocabulary Levels Test, which is in English, has 18 items (Laufer & Nation, 1999, as cited in Cobb, 2019). I modified the PVLTL because I needed to select quality items that have acceptable difficulty and discrimination levels. To do this, I administered two pilot tests on eight students using items from different versions of the PVLTL. For the first vocabulary test, 40 items were pilot tested and underwent item analysis. The recommended values for test items are a Difficulty level of .25-.75 and a Discrimination Index of .20 or higher (Brophy, 2019). Only 10 items passed the item analysis. To complete the number of items for the final version, I piloted another set, consisting of 35 vocabulary test items to the same participants. Another 10 items passed the item analysis. A total of 20 items were in the final version

and the test was administered through a Google Form. The Google Form was made into a quiz which instructed the participants to supply the missing word for each sentence. I inputted the answer key and assigned one point for each item. Once the students answered the test, the Google Form evaluated each item as correct or incorrect based on the answer key, and computed each student's score.

Writing Test. To measure the writing performance of the students, I administered a writing test in English (see Appendix E). The students were asked to watch a YouTube video, "Are You Living an Insta Lie? Social Media Vs. Reality" (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0EFHbruKEmw>) and were instructed to write an essay answering the question "*How do you feel about using social media after watching this video? Please share the positive and negative effects of social media on your life.*" They were also asked to support their answers with personal experiences, as texts with exemplification were discussed in the senior high school students' Reading and Writing Skills subject (DepEd, 2013).

Because of errors in test proctoring in the initial data gathering sessions, a second version of the writing task was administered to students who did not finish the first version within the proctored time. They were asked to watch another YouTube video, "Why We Can't Stop Scrolling" (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uBkeKv_6U4c) and were instructed to write an essay answering the question: *How do you feel about the time you spend on online activities (e.g. social media, gaming) after watching this video? What advice would you give to someone with an internet addiction?* Like the first version, they were asked to support their answers with personal experiences.

The writing tests were validated by three teachers with Master's degrees, pilot tested on eight students and were administered using Google Forms. For both versions, students were given 40 minutes to plan, write, and revise their essay with a minimum of 300 words or 15-20 sentences.

Each of the 99 essays was evaluated by three English teachers who have at least five years' experience teaching English, two of whom have finished their Master's degrees in English, and one who has finished her academic requirements for a Master's degree. They used a 20-point rubric that covers focus, support, organization, word choice, and sentence structure, grammar mechanics and spelling. The average of the three sets of scores were computed for analysis.

Use of Google Forms for Quantitative Research Instruments. The questionnaire about the participants' IDLE activities, the vocabulary test, and the writing test were all administered with one Google Form which collected their responses.

Qualitative Phase

Semi-structured Interviews. To determine in greater detail the IDLE activities of the participants and how these activities affect their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, I used a semi-structured interview schedule (see Appendix G), adapting Lee's (2017) interview protocol. I asked the students three questions about their different kinds of IDLE activities and how these have affected their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The students' family members were asked the same questions from their perspective about the students' IDLE activities. I had these

questions validated by three teachers with Master's degrees and conducted pilot test interviews on two students and two parents.

I modified Lee's (2018) interview procedure, and I conducted the interviews with 20 students via Messenger, Viber, and Zoom. They were recorded using OBS Studio. These interviews were conducted in English, Hiligaynon, and/or Filipino (Tagalog), depending on which language the interviewee was comfortable in. The participants were purposefully selected based on the responses on the first questionnaire and their PVLТ and writing task scores (see Appendix G for the interview protocol). They were selected because they reported high amounts of time on IDLE activities daily (11-31 hours), and yielded satisfactory scores in the vocabulary test (11-17 points out of a total of 20) and in the essay test (15-19.33 points out of a total of 20) compared to the rest of the participants. The reason for these criteria is that previous research has shown that more time spent on IDLE activities is related to higher vocabulary knowledge and writing skills (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Olsson, 2016; Jensen, 2016; Sundqvist, 2019). The interviews lasted for 10-15 minutes to obtain deeper insights between the students' IDLE experiences and vocabulary knowledge and writing skills (Lee & Dressman, 2018). Afterwards, I identified, coded, and synthesized recurring themes related to the research questions.

Table 3
Summary of Research Instruments

Quantitative Research Instruments	Purpose	Description
Questionnaire for Students	To collect the students' demographic information, to establish the IDLE activities they engage in, and the daily time they spend on these activities.	The students were asked to indicate how much time they spend on each IDLE activity.
Productive Vocabulary Levels Test	To measure the students' vocabulary performance.	The students were asked to answer 20 vocabulary test items.
Writing Test	To measure the writing performance of the students.	The students were asked to write essays answering writing prompts.
Interview Protocols for Students and Family Members	To determine in greater detail the IDLE activities of the participants and how these activities affect their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.	The students and family members were asked about the students' IDLE activities and how these have affected their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Data Gathering Procedures
Figure 2

Process of Data Collection

Figure 2 summarizes the main steps of the data collection. The first step I did was to secure permission from the principal of the school and its senior high school department head. Afterwards, the researcher-made questionnaires, tests, and interview protocols were validated with the expert evaluation of three experienced English teachers who have Master's degrees. They evaluated the research instruments using a modified version of the criteria for the validation of research instruments by Good & Scates (1972, as cited in Oducado, 2021). The English teachers also gave suggestions to improve the instruments. One teacher said that I should have indicated why personal information such as the participants' names are needed for the study. I addressed this suggestion by placing an explanation that they may be invited to an interview in the second phase of the study. Another teacher suggested that I should shorten the introduction before the questionnaire, which I did not do because I had to inform the participants about the important details of the study before they could express their consent to participate. Another comment was that the 30-minute time limit for essay writing I had originally set may be too short, so I increased the time limit to 40 minutes.

Pilot Test

The improved research instruments, namely the questionnaire for students, the Productive Vocabulary Levels Test, the writing test, and the interview protocol, were then pilot tested on eight students from the same school. The interview protocol for family members were also pilot tested on two mothers who at the time had sons at the same school.

Table 4
Pilot Participants' Profile

Sex Assigned at Birth	Number of Participants
Grade 11	
Female	2
Male	2
Total	4
Grade 12	
Female	2
Male	2
Total	4
Parents	
Female	2
Male	0
Total	2

A pilot test tests the validity of the questionnaires and tests and determines whether the procedures are feasible or susceptible to bias (Bhandari, 2021). I followed the following steps:

1. The purpose of the tests was explained to the participants.
2. I asked the pilot participants to indicate how many hours they spend for each IDLE activity.
3. I computed the sum of the total time spent on IDLE.
4. One of them had a suggestion to include more examples of IDLE, so I included other examples of IDLE in the final questionnaire, namely (a)

listening to podcasts in English, (b) taking online courses in English for leisure, and (c) voice or video calls with other people in English using platforms like Messenger, Discord, WhatsApp, and Viber.

5. For the vocabulary test, I had them answer 40 items from different versions of the Productive Vocabulary Levels Test (PVLТ). The participants also answered the writing test, which I scored using the 20-point rubric.
6. I then computed the Pearson correlation between the time spent on IDLE activities and the vocabulary scores. There was a very strong positive correlation between the two variables, $r(6) = .72, p = .044$. I also computed the Pearson correlation between time spent on IDLE activities and the writing scores, and there was a weak negative correlation between the two variables, $r(6) = -.09, p = .838$
7. The Difficulty Level and Discrimination Index were computed for the 40 vocabulary test items. The recommended values for test items are a difficulty level of .25-.75 and a Discrimination Index of .20 or higher (Brophy, 2019). Only 10 items passed the item analysis, so another pilot test was held with 35 items from other versions of the PVLТ, and another 10 items passed the item analysis. A total of 20 items were included in the final version of the test.
8. I tested the interview protocol on two pilot participants, one male and one female, who had also taken the quantitative pilot test. One student gave the suggestion to specify the time period when the interviewees' vocabulary and writing skills were affected by IDLE.

9. Following Lee (2017), I modified the final interview protocol to ask questions about the participants' specific IDLE activities in the last 6 months.
10. I tested the interview protocol for family members on two mothers with sons who at the time were outgoing Grade 12 students. The mothers said that the pilot interviews were already good and did not give suggestions for improvement.

Quantitative Data Collection

After the pilot test, I conducted the main collection of the quantitative data by administering the questionnaire about IDLE activities and the vocabulary and writing tests via a Google Form and Google Meet. I followed these steps:

1. The purpose of the tests was explained to the participants.
2. In the first data gathering session, I had a full hour to proctor the questionnaire and the tests, but only 25 were able to accomplish all the instruments.
3. I then borrowed online class periods from their teachers to be able to reach more participants. However, since the class periods were only 40 minutes each, these participants were only able to finish the questionnaire and the vocabulary test.
4. I developed a second version of the writing test.
5. I held more proctored periods for the rest of the participants to answer the second version of the writing test.

6. I also administered the full instrument for one hour to the rest of the students who had not taken it previously. A total of 99 students were able to answer the quantitative research instruments.
7. The quantitative data was then analyzed to select the participants who reported high amounts of time on IDLE activities daily and yielded satisfactory scores in the vocabulary and writing tests. These participants were chosen for interviews in the second, qualitative phase of the study.

Qualitative Data Collection

After selecting the 20 student participants and their family members, I conducted the qualitative data collection through Messenger voice calls, Viber voice calls, and Zoom by following these steps:

1. I started recording the calls using OBS studio.
2. The purpose of the tests was explained to the participants.
3. I asked the three interview questions to each of the participants and took note of their responses.
4. We had 10–15-minute conversations about how the internet and digital devices has affected the students' English skills, and how these have affected their vocabulary and writing skills. The interviews were in English, Hiligaynon, and/or Filipino (Tagalog), depending on the language the interviewees were comfortable in.
5. The interviews were then transcribed verbatim by myself and two other transcriptionists who are native Hiligaynon speakers and are proficient in English and Filipino.

Ethical Considerations

Following the guidelines of the Institution Research Ethics Committee (IREC) of UPOU, I oriented the participants of the following information before the data gathering: (1) the duration—the participants were informed about how long the questionnaire, tests and interviews would take, and the possibility that they may be called again for an interview; (2) the risks—the participants were informed that they would answer the questionnaire and tests from the safety of their home and that their participation has no bearing on their academic grade, and those who would be invited for an interview have a right to refuse to answer questions that make him/her uncomfortable; (3) the benefits—the students were told that their participation in the study would contribute to finding new ways to improve English teaching and learning for Filipino senior high school students; (4) the meal allowance—the participants were told that they would receive Grab vouchers worth PHP 100 each as a meal allowance for their time and involvement in the research, and these were sent to them; (5) confidentiality—I informed the participants that I would maintain the confidentiality by protecting the names of the school and the participants; names were changed in writing the research; (6) sharing the results—the participants were told how and when the results would be shared, and will be informed if the research findings will be shared more broadly in publications and conferences; (7) right to refuse or withdraw—I reiterated that participation in the study was voluntary, and that participants had the right to refuse or to withdraw; (8) data management—I discussed that I will store the data until the study is over, and that I will delete it afterwards; and (9) contact details—the participants can contact me during the duration of the study about any concern that they have.

The participants, both the students and the family members, also filled out an informed consent form via Google Forms. The document includes the purpose of the research and the reason for participant selection.

Quantitative Data Analysis Procedures

Informal Digital Learning of English of SHS Students

The first research question asked about what IDLE activities Filipino senior high school students are engaged in. To determine this, I computed the mean and standard deviation for each preselected IDLE activity: (1) Video, (2) Social Media, (3) Music, (4) Digital Gaming, (5) Reading, (6) Social Reading Platforms, and (7) Other IDLE activities. The mean and the standard deviation were used to summarize the typical value of hours spent daily for each IDLE activity.

Correlation Between Time Spent on IDLE Activities and Vocabulary and Writing Performance

The second research question asked about the correlation between the participants' time spent on IDLE activities and their (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance. For each participant, I computed the sum of the different IDLE activities to determine how much time is spent on IDLE. To determine the vocabulary scores, I used the automatic grading feature of Google Forms. For the writing test scores, I computed the Cronbach's alpha to determine the interrater reliability of the three sets of scores of the tests evaluated by the three English teachers. Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient can be used to compute for interrater reliability if there are more than two raters (Multon, 2010). The Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient for

the three sets of scores was 0.8, which is considered good (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). Furthermore, I computed the averages of the three sets of scores.

Afterwards, I used Jamovi to compute the Pearson Correlation Coefficient between the variables (1) time spent on IDLE activities and the vocabulary test scores, and (2) time spent on IDLE activities and the averages of the writing test scores.

Qualitative Data Analysis Procedures

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students' Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills

The interview data was used to answer the first research question, which asks about what IDLE activities Filipino SHS students are engaged in, as well as the third research question, which asks about the ways by which IDLE activities affect the participants' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills.

Adapting Lee's (2018) procedure, the two transcriptionists and I transcribed each interview verbatim. Using the approach of Braun and Clarke (2006), I then read interview transcripts to familiarize myself with the data. Afterwards, using an inductive approach, I identified, coded, and synthesized recurring themes related to the research questions with the help of the Delve Qualitative Analysis Tool. I then wrote the analysis of the data, describing themes and what they mean. I also included some examples or quotes from the data as evidence (Caulfied, 2022). The participants' names were changed to protect their identity and confidentiality. The qualitative results were used to support and explain the quantitative results.

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This research presents empirical evidence to provide a better understanding of the IDLE activities among Filipino senior high school students. I answered the following questions:

1. What Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) activities are Filipino senior high school students engaged in?
2. Is there a correlation between the time spent on IDLE activities of Filipino senior high school students and their:
 - a. Vocabulary performance?
 - b. Writing performance?
3. In what ways do IDLE activities affect senior high school students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills?

Informal Digital Learning of English Activities of Filipino Senior High School Students

The first research question asked about the Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE) activities that Filipino senior high school students are engaged in. The survey data shows that they engage in a variety of IDLE activities, namely using social media, watching videos, listening to music, playing digital games, reading digital content, and other IDLE activities such as podcasts and video calls.

Table 5*Mean of Daily Time Spent on IDLE per Category (in hours)*

IDLE Category	Examples	M	SD
Social Media	<i>Communicating on social media sites (e.g., TikTok, Instagram, Twitter, Reddit)</i>	4.22	3.32
Videos	<i>Watching online films, videos, series, and streaming services (e.g., Netflix, YouTube)</i>	3.44	2.04
Music	<i>Listening to music with English lyrics (e.g., Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube Music)</i>	2.79	2.56
Digital Games	<i>Playing mobile, online, PC, console games, or other digital games (e.g., Mobile Legends, Genshin Impact, League of Legends)</i>	2.74	2.40
Reading	<i>Reading online content from websites or eBooks (e.g., Kindle eBooks, Wikipedia articles, news websites like Rappler and Inquirer)</i>	1.32	2.12
Social Reading	<i>Reading and/or writing on social reading platforms (e.g., Wattpad)</i>	0.92	1.60
Other IDLE Activities	<i>(e.g., Listening to English podcasts, taking online courses in English for leisure, voice, or video calls with other people in English using messaging platforms like Messenger, Discord, WhatsApp, and Viber)</i>	3.20	4.09

As seen in Table 5, they also reported spending the most time on social media, with an average time of 4.22 hours a day, followed by videos, other IDLE activities, music, digital games, reading, and social reading, which had the least daily average time of 0.92 hours. The results are comparable to Lee's (2017), in which the Korean EFL students reported engaging in a variety of IDLE activities, like the use of social media, watching videos, and video-chatting. The variety of IDLE activities that the students choose to engage in may be explained by learner autonomy (Holec, 1981), because the students seem to select what kind of English content they want to watch, read, or listen to, and through these activities, they learn English.

The participants spending the most time on social media is expected, as the results are congruent with the report that Filipinos spend the most time on social media worldwide, with an average of 4 hours and 15 minutes a day (Chua, 2021). However, the present study's results contrast with Niitemaa's (2020) research, in which Finnish students reported less daily English exposure to social media and daily English exposure to music and films. Social media has positive and negative effects on language learning. Social media has impacted language learning because it may negatively affect grammar, spelling, and sentence construction by exposing the learners to errors in writing (Saha, 2019). However, other learners experienced improvement in their writing style, reading skills, lexical variation, communication skills because of social media (Muftah, 2022; Haque, 2018). The learners in this study may have been exposed to and affected by social media's positive and negative effects on language learning.

It is also worth noting that the students spend the least time on reading and social reading. This is a concerning result, as reading is an essential skill in language

learning. However, this is expected as the general population of Filipinos do not seem to be very interested in reading (Co, 2021). The results show that the participants seem to prefer to consume content on social media—which are full of errors in grammar, spelling, and sentence construction—rather than read eBooks. This exposure to content on social media may have negatively influenced their writing, which will be explored in a succeeding discussion.

Two students indicated in the survey that they would multitask different IDLE activities, such as having voice or video calls during online games. Moreover, when the hours of all the IDLE activities were added to get the total daily time spent on IDLE for each participant, 23 of them had a total daily time of more than 24 hours in a day on IDLE activities, which may be indicative of multitasking or overlapping of different IDLE categories (e.g., watching videos and reading on social media). This multitasking behavior is comparable to previous literature, which shows that teenagers spend over 11 hours of daily media consumption in multitasking (Uncapher & Wagner, 2018).

The qualitative data also gives an insight about what IDLE activities the students are engaged in. In the interviews, the students described different categories of their IDLE engagement, including how they learned English from these.

Using Social Media

Five students cited a variety of social media platforms as an IDLE activity, such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok. The interview data shows that the students engage in a variety of activities on social media and reported that they learn English from them. It is also noted that the participants engage in IDLE activities that

overlap, such as watching videos and reading on social media, similar to the findings of Lee (2017).

Jennifer, a female student, said that her English has grown because the language is predominant in social media:

I think *daw mas nag-grow ang English ko* because when using social media or the internet, *mas gina-use ang English in tanan nga categories*, like social media...or even Tiktoks, so *ma-read mo siya* and *ma-hear mo siya* everyday. (I think my English has grown because when using social media or the internet, English is used more in all categories, like social media...or even Tiktoks, so one can read and hear it everyday.)

It seems that Jennifer is immersed in English content because of social media, which has affected her English learning. This is expected because social media provides opportunities for learners to improve their reading and writing. They also may read new text and phrases to improve their vocabulary (Al-Jarrah, et al., 2019).

Vincent, a male student, shared his experience of using Facebook to read the news:

I think *ang pinakagrabe ko gid ginausar* is well, Facebook and, *kay ti, may mga news da*, reading the news, or online news articles. (I think the one I use the most is Facebook because it has the news, reading the news or online news articles.)

The mother of Annika had a similar response, saying that she would share articles for her children to read:

She reads article and sometimes *ginapasa ko man na sa ila* what I can find in sa Instagram. *Kung ano ang makita ko sa Internet, ginapasa ko man na*

sa ila to my kids' group chat. (She reads articles and sometimes I pass what I can find on Instagram. What I can find on the Internet, I also pass [these] to my kids' group chat.)

Social media, especially Facebook, is a major source of English news. Other platforms include YouTube, Twitter, and Instagram (Martin, 2018). The news are authentic resources of language learning (Roberts, 2014). Reading the news has been found to enhance vocabulary, grammar, idioms, and phrases (Sultana & Singh, 2022; Preethi, 2020). Because of these reasons, it is therefore probable that the students learned English from reading the news.

Watching Videos

Similar to social media, eight students cited different platforms where they watch English content, such as Netflix and YouTube. One student, Brianna, said that “I think [videos] affected me in a good way because a lot of videos ...has changed the way I talk, express myself, or write for my school.” Agustin similarly reported, “I learned English through watching movies, series, and watching YouTube videos.”

The six other students had similar responses, like how one follows the way of speaking of celebrities in their YouTube channels, and another who looks up unfamiliar words they encounter while watching movies and series.

Nine family members of the participants also reported the English learning of the participants through videos, such as the sister of Anya, who observed that:

She really honed and improved her [English] skills through watching *mga* English shows such as *Miss ang mga Simpsons na bala Miss...mga BoJack Horseman...they really used like good deep English words nga maka learn*

ka gid bala Miss sa English *nila nga gina* use (they really used good deep English words that one can learn the English that they use).

From this excerpt, it is apparent that Anya learned new words, like “blasé” from watching American animated television series such as *9-1-1*. Other family members gave similar observations, such as a mother who likewise claimed that her son’s English skills improved from watching YouTube and Netflix videos. A sister reported that she and the participant had been watching a lot of American films since they were young, which affected their speaking in English. Another family member said that the more her sister became immersed in movies and YouTube videos, the more confident she became in speaking English. This learner growing self-confident in her use of English may be explained by Krashen’s (2018) Affective Filter hypothesis, because she was exposed to and learned the English language in a comfortable environment with a low affective filter with less negative emotions like embarrassment or fear (Lewis, 2020).

The interview responses about watching videos provide an insight into the English learning experiences of the participants. Several of the participants shared how English videos helped them in the students’ speaking and vocabulary. These results can be explained by their experience of being immersed in digital media with spoken and written English (videos are often with subtitles). Because of these, they may have “picked up” (Hulstijn, 2013) spoken English and English vocabulary. This is similar to Lee’s (2018) findings, in which Korean EFL students watched English movies, series, and YouTube videos, and acquired English vocabulary and expressions.

Listening to Music

Another IDLE activity reported by the students is listening to music. Eight of them mentioned that they would listen to music while doing other IDLE activities. For instance, Jennifer stated:

Sometimes if I'm playing video games with my friends, *gapamusic man ko*, and also if *gascroll lang sa Tiktok*, *gapamusic man ko*. (Sometimes if I'm playing video games with my friends, I play music, and also if I scroll through Tiktok, I also play music.)

The other students had similar responses, such as listening to music while reading or scrolling through online shopping platforms. Aside from other IDLE activities, students also said that they would listen to music while doing non-IDLE activities, such as Cole, who states, "I usually listen to music so that I have an accompaniment. I usually put [music] as a background when I do my studies, when I'm doing my essay, for example." Another student said that he would listen to music while doing school work that does not require a lot of effort.

Three parents of the students also observed this multitasking behavior among their children. For example, the mother of Lizzie said:

Siguro makita ko man kis-a naka earphone siya, although *kis-a ga amo na ga cellphone pa gid ga laptop pa gid*. *Kis-a gasulat nga may earphones pa gid*. (I see her with her earphones on while using her cellphone and her laptop. Sometimes she writes with her earphones on.)

Several of the participants said that they listen to English music while doing something else, like another IDLE activity (e.g., scrolling through social media or

chatting with friends) or other non-IDLE activities, like schoolwork. The family members have expressed that they notice this multitasking. The SHS students appear to be able to engage in different IDLE activities at once. These results are comparable with previous literature that teenagers engage in multitasking by concurrently engaging in different digital activities, or by doing a digital activity while doing other things, like classwork or homework (Shih, 2013). Multitasking can affect language learning depending on whether the person is multitasking to distract oneself, or they are multitasking in an informed or intentional way. A learner who engages in distracted multitasking may recall fewer words than a person with no distractions (Middlebrooks, et al., 2017). On the other hand, multitasking mindfully while learning a language can be productive by studying while exercising or listening to podcasts while doing activities that do not require mental concentration, like household tasks (Koyfman, 2019). In the present study, the students seem to be engaged in distracted multitasking, as they appear not to listen to music with the intention of learning English, but just as an accompaniment to another activity they are doing. However, it is also possible that these learners may be learning English incidentally (Hulstijin, 2013), “picking up” new words and expressions from the music they listen to.

Playing Digital Games

Six students mentioned that they would play online or digital games while talking to their friends or copleayers via Discord, a Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP) and instant messaging platform. For instance, Vincent reported:

Like *mga* Discord, *amu gid na siya*–Discord and while playing a game, *kay para maka-istoryahanay kamo*, especially *mga* war zone, you need to

communicate with each other *para--let's say ang isa ara sa tubang balay gabantay kontra*, so if *may kontra na nagsulod*, he can communicate with me, and other team. (We use Discord while playing a game so that we can speak to one another especially in war zones, you need to communicate with each other so that--let's say one is in front of the house waiting for his opponent, so if the opponent enters, he can communicate with me and the other team.)

In this excerpt, the participant was able to give a concrete situation in online gaming where communication with other players via Discord is needed. Other students had similar responses, with one saying that Discord is the most important communication platform in games. Another student said that he communicates in English with people he does not know:

Another would be, through video games, actually, because in some video games, there's a voice talk, like a chat feature, where you can speak with other people. Usually, the people that I play with are--sometimes they are people that I do not know, so the medium of speaking is English.

Two brothers stated that they would play online games with the student-participants and use communication platforms while doing so; the brother of the Vincent said, "We play online games together, we would turn on like the walkie-talkie in the phone apps." Playing online/digital games while talking to friends using a platform like Discord is another example of multitasking, which is simultaneously accessing two or more forms of media (Becker et al., 2013). Like the discussion on listening to music, these students using Discord while playing digital games may be engaging in distracted multitasking (Middlebrooks, et al., 2017), as they do not seem

to use either activity to intentionally learn English. However, it is also possible that they have learned English incidentally (Hulstijn, 2013) through these activities, “picking up” new words and expressions from the games that they play.

Reading Digital Content

Eight students cited reading online or digital content as an IDLE activity. For example, Kelsey said, “I like to read *mga* eBooks and *magscroll* sa social media and I think *ang mga* words *nga* I get from there... I try to apply man when I speak English.” Mimi gave a similar response: “I learned English or *amu ma na* from ebooks. *Ang sa* ebook, *gaka* learn *ko* actually *kay gina-annotate ko* ang books.” (I learned English from eBooks. I learn from eBooks because I annotate the books). Ismael highlighted how he uses social media to update himself: “[On social media apps], I would just be scrolling through, just reading, or looking at what is happening right now.”

The students’ reading online texts and eBooks seems to be congruent with the 2017 report by the National Book Development Board that Filipino youth respondents spend more time on eBooks than other formats, with 14.16 hours a month. Some participants in the present study also said that they learn new words from reading online and digital texts. This can be compared to Peters’ (2018) study, which found that Flemish teenagers preferred online reading to printed text, and that there is a positive relationship between exposure to learners’ vocabulary knowledge and browsing the internet.

In general, the students mentioned two sources of digital content that they read: online content from social media and eBooks. One cited an added feature of reading

eBooks, which is being able to annotate. Seven family members likewise said that the student-participants read a substantial amount of digital content, such as eBooks.

For example, the father of Vina stated: “We did get her an e-reader...which I think greatly influenced her English. The beauty of an e-reader is that if you run into a word that you don't understand, you click on the word and it gives a definition.” Digital or online reading is fundamentally different from reading print materials (Nordquist, 2017) because it is “nonlinear;” when one reads information digitally, they can go to other sources using hyperlinks (Carter, 2013, as cited by Nordquist, 2017). These help the student deepen their understanding or learn the definition of new or confusing terms (Hurt, 2023). In the present study, the interactive nature of digital reading may have contributed to their learning of English, as they can, for example, easily look up the meanings of unfamiliar words.

Engaging in Other IDLE Activities (Discord, Podcasts, Voice and Video Calls)

Four students reported other IDLE activities different from the identified categories, such as using Discord, answering an online test and listening to podcasts. For example, Annika said: “*Pwede mo lang ma-play na daw* podcasts Miss, while you were doing something.” (One can play podcasts, Miss, while doing something). Podcasts can positively affect English language learning, specifically listening comprehension (Abdulrahman, et al., 2018). Moreover, one can learn a language while listening to podcasts while doing tasks that do not require much concentration (Koyfman, 2019). Annika may have improved her listening comprehension skills as she listened to podcasts while multitasking because she was exposed to authentic English input; podcasts are recorded conversations. Moreover, she can choose the

podcasts that are interesting to her, so she can be motivated to listen and learn from them (Abdulrahman et al., 2018).

Another student, Vincent, claimed that he learned a new word from an online test:

I was reading a--*indi siya* article, *daw* test siya, actually, some test online that I took up, then I discovered the word latter. *Una una daw indi kainchindi kung ano ni nga* latter man, *dayon ginsearch ko siya, dayon it means gali amo na siya.* (At first, I did not understand the word “latter,” then I searched for it).

Vincent seems to have encountered this new word incidentally (Hulstijn, 2013) while answering an online test, leading him to look up the meaning of the new word.

One family member affirmed that her daughter would listen to many English podcasts. Moreover, three family members stated that they have relatives abroad from English-speaking countries, and reported that selected students would communicate with these relatives via voice call or video call. For example, Vincent’s brother said that Vincent would use his phone and laptop to talk to their relatives in the US. The mother of Agustin had a similar response:

He talks [via voice call or video chat] a lot to his Auntie, both Aunties from both sides because my sister is in New Zealand and his Tita from the sister of his Dad is from the US...maybe that helps.

According to previous literature, synchronous video computer-mediated communication (SVMC) such as Skype, FaceTime, and Zoom gives second language learners opportunities to interact with speakers of the target language (Kessler, et al., 2021). Vincent and Agustin seem to have applied their English communication skills

while talking to their relatives via SVMC because they have access to authentic linguistic input and interact with more proficient or native speakers of English (Yu, 2022).

Parental Influence on Children's IDLE Activities

A noteworthy finding in this study is the role of parents in supporting and regulating the IDLE activities of their children. Six parents expressed their influence on their children in this regard, such as Vina's father:

We try not...to give her too much access to anything online, but we notice that she likes, so we did get her an e-reader which I think greatly influenced her English, as well as those DVDs, whatever shows that she would watch. Netflix is not a big thing at home but you know that I can't stop them. She's now sixteen and she has her own device.

From this excerpt, it is apparent that the father would regulate his daughter's online access, but also gave her an e-reader that he reports helped her learn English. Another parent, a mother, exposed her daughter to English media from an early age, which may explain why the daughter prefers to communicate in English. Two parents said that they would discuss what their children would find on the internet, such as articles or new words. For example, the mother of Clark said,

At times, even me, *basta may opportunity kami nga naga-watch together, even I, gapamangkot ko sa iya. If hindi siya aware, gina-search gid ya namon. Dason gina-discuss man namon nga "What does it mean?" "Sa context, paano siya gingamit?"* (At times, even me, when we have the opportunity to watch together, even I ask him [the meaning of the word]. If

he's not aware, we really discuss it. Then we discuss, "What does it mean?"
"How is it used in context?")

It seems evident in this excerpt how the mother would support her son's IDLE activities by discussing the meanings of words and how they are used. Similarly, another parent, the father of Rico, stated,

I told him that for every word *nga* he wouldn't understand [when watching *Suits*]...*mapause* mo man lang ang movie then you can search *ya* some meaning sa Internet...*amo lang na hambal ko sa iya*, at least *makalearn siya* one, one word a day. (I told him that for every word he wouldn't understand [when watching *Suits*], he can just pause the movie and search the meaning of the words on the internet. I told him, at least you can learn one word a day.)

This excerpt likewise shows how the father would support his child's IDLE through watching a series by encouraging him to pause the video and looking up the meanings of unfamiliar words. It is apparent from these results that the parents of the students who have the resources support the IDLE activities of their children, which may not be true for all families. The results imply that parents are a major influence in their children's IDLE activities. As primary educators of their children, they would give their children access to devices and the internet (Office of Educational Technology, n.d.). They also support their children to achieve bilingualism by exposing them to different kinds of English digital content which in turn influences their English learning (Lindgren and Munoz, 2013; Nam, 2016).

Synthesis

The first research question asked about the IDLE activities that Filipino senior high school students are engaged in. The quantitative results show that they spend different amounts of time on various IDLE activities, the most being social media. Social media may have had positive and negative effects on their language learning (Muftah, 2022; Saha, 2019; Haque, 2018). According to the qualitative results, the respondents claim that their English has improved because of social media and that it is a source of news, which is an authentic resource for language learning (Roberts, 2014). The students likewise reported learning English from watching videos.

Another noteworthy result was that students spend the least time on reading and social reading, which is a concerning result, as reading is an essential skill in language learning. That they spend more time on social media, with all its errors in grammar, spelling, and sentence construction, may have affected their writing.

Some participants claimed that they multitask while listening to music and doing other tasks. Other students reported that they would play digital games while using Discord, another example of multitasking. Previous literature classifies this as distracted multitasking (Middlebrooks, et al., 2017) because the students do not appear to be engaging in IDLE activities with the intention of learning English, but it is possible that they have been learning English incidentally (Hulstijin, 2013), “picking up” new words and expressions from the music they listen to and the games that they play.

Another interesting finding is about digital reading. Some participants reported reading online texts and eBooks, which have an interactive feature because they may include hyperlinks that can lead them to other sources (Carter, 2013, as cited by

Nordquist, 2017). For example, one participant mentioned being able to click on a word in an eReader and finding the definition. This ease of use may have contributed to their English language learning.

Some students reported engaging in other IDLE activities, such as podcasts, which have been found to positively affect listening comprehension in English (Abdulrahman, et al., 2018), and can be done with multitasking (Koyfman, 2019). An online test was also mentioned, as well as voice or video calls with other English speakers. Synchronous video computer-mediated communication gives second language learners opportunities to interact with speakers of the target language (Kessler, et al., 2021).

The results also show that parents with resources both support and regulate their children's IDLE activities, such as giving their children access to devices and the internet. These resources in turn influence the children's English learning.

In summary, the participants engage in a variety of IDLE activities and have reported learning English from these activities which may have been affected by multitasking and parental influence.

IDLE and Vocabulary Performance

The second research question asked whether there is a correlation between the time SHS students spend on IDLE activities and their (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance.

There was a weak positive correlation between time spent on IDLE and vocabulary performance, $r(97) = .07$, $p = 0.492$. The results confirm the null

hypotheses that there is no significant relationship between time spent on IDLE and vocabulary performance.

Table 6

Correlation between Total IDLE Time and Vocabulary Scores

Variables			Interpretation
Total IDLE Time and Vocabulary Scores	Pearson's <i>r</i>	.07	Weak positive correlation
	<i>p</i> -value	.492	

Although the quantitative results show that the time spent on IDLE activities does not have a significant correlation with the vocabulary scores, the qualitative data suggests that the participants did learn new vocabulary and elements of writing from their engagement in IDLE activities. The lack of association between IDLE and vocabulary performance is in contrast with earlier findings (Sundqvist and Wikstrom, 2015; Jensen, 2016; Peters, 2018; Sundqvist, 2019). The results about IDLE and vocabulary are comparable to Lee's (2017) study in that there is no significant relationship between IDLE quantity and vocabulary scores. The results of the present study imply that time does not predict whether the learners learn new vocabulary, but the kind of language learning may do so. Lee's (2017) study showed that the quality of IDLE, that is a combination of form- and meaning-focused language learning, is positively associated with vocabulary outcomes. In the qualitative findings of my study, ten learners reported form-focused language learning such as using Google or an online dictionary. Several of the interview participants also said that they would engage in meaning-focused activities, such as watching videos, reading online content, communicating on social media, and playing online games. Some reported that they

learned new words from context while engaging in these activities. The presence of both form- and meaning-focused IDLE language learning among the interview participants may explain their claims that they indeed learn vocabulary from engaging in IDLE activities, even if there is a lack of relationship between the time they spend engaging in these and their vocabulary scores.

IDLE and Writing Performance

On the other hand, there was a weak negative correlation between the time spent on IDLE and writing performance, $r(97) = -.16, p = .107$.

Table 7

Correlation between Total IDLE Time and Writing Scores

Variables		Interpretation	
Total IDLE Time and Writing Scores	Pearson's <i>r</i>	-.16	Weak negative correlation
	<i>p</i> -value	.107	

The results confirm the null hypotheses that there is also an insignificant correlation between time spent on IDLE and writing performance, which is in contrast with Olsson's (2016) findings that students who had greater exposure to extramural English performed well in different aspects of writing performance. The results of the present study imply that time does not predict whether the learners learn new writing skills. A factor that may have contributed to the weak correlation and the many low writing scores of the participants is the fact that they were not allowed to use Google or other resources while constructing their essay. In other online writing tasks, they may have been used to digital resources such as the dictionary or grammar websites to improve their written work.

However, in the qualitative phase of the study, the interview participants report that they learned writing skills from their IDLE activities. These claims may be supported by their high scores in the writing tests which were rated by three teachers. Moreover, the kind of activities the interview participants may also have contributed to their writing skills; they reported that they would read digital content which influenced their writing, particularly when these texts provide modeling for writing style and diction.

It is worth noting that four of the participants observed that much of online English is composed of informal language and slang, with many errors and shortcuts. I revisited the English teachers' ratings of the 99 students' essays, focusing on the criterion of sentence structure, grammar, mechanics, and spelling, which is equivalent to a total of four points. The first teacher's ratings had an average of 3.12, while the second had an average of 2.87, and the third had 2.60. From this data, it seems that the teachers generally rated the essays three points and below, which means that most of the students fall short of the perfect score, and may have committed errors in sentence structure, grammar, mechanics, and spelling. These could perhaps be attributed to exposure to slang or informal English encountered online, which may increase the grammatical errors in writing in English among students (Funmilayo, 2020). Even if the interview participants claim that they learned English skills from their IDLE activities, their unsatisfactory scores in grammar and mechanics may be explained by their exposure to erroneous English, although more research needs to be done to validate this.

Synthesis

The results show that there is no significant relationship between their time spent on IDLE and both their vocabulary performance and writing performance. The results imply that time does not predict whether the learners learn new vocabulary or develop writing skills. However, the kinds of activities may contribute to their vocabulary and writing development. Engagement in form- and meaning-focused language learning could have led them to learn new words. Reading digital content that provides modeling for writing style and diction could have influenced their writing skills.

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students' Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills

The third research question asked about the ways IDLE activities affect SHS students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The next section features the qualitative findings about IDLE and vocabulary knowledge.

Table 8

The Final Themes about IDLE and Vocabulary Knowledge and Writing Skills

Themes about IDLE and Vocabulary Knowledge	Themes about IDLE and Writing Skills
Curiosity About the Meanings of Words	Learning from Models of Writing from IDLE
Learning Vocabulary in Context	Improving Writing through IDLE
New Words Learned	Becoming a Better Writer by Reading Digital Content
Using New Words Learned	Learning Punctuations from the Internet Writing Facilitated by Interactive Reading and Writing

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students' Vocabulary Knowledge

Curiosity About the Meanings of Words

Ten students expressed that when they encounter an unfamiliar word, they get motivated to look it up using Google or an online dictionary. For instance, Justin said, "Because when I watch a movie, the subtitles are always on, so when there are words I'm unfamiliar with, I just search on the internet for the word and how to use it in a sentence." He shared a word that he learned, which is "perspicacity."

Lizzie had also reported:

Before when I started reading, there is a lot of new words that I wasn't familiar with and I learned a lot of them, of new vocabulary, and also I

Googled them from the Internet so and now it's so easy. It's easier *na* for me to understand some new vocabulary.

The other students had similar responses, that when they encounter unfamiliar words when watching or reading English content, they would look up their meanings online.

Eight family members affirmed this finding, saying that they noticed this kind of behavior among the students. For example, Clark's mother said, "*Amo lang na-notice ko nga if may ma-encounter siya nga word nga not familiar sa iya, automatic, gina-search niya.*" (If he encounters a word he's not familiar with, he automatically searches for it.) Two parents said that they would encourage their children to search for the meanings of unfamiliar words. These findings imply that the students have their own initiative to find definitions of words that they find interesting and that they encounter through digital means. The concept of learner autonomy, or taking charge of one's own learning (Holec, 1981) may be evident here.

These results are congruent with Lee's (2017) findings that English language learners engage in form-focused IDLE activities, which involve the student learning the accuracy of linguistic forms using digital tools (e.g., looking up an English word using a dictionary).

Learning Vocabulary in Context

Four participants related how they learned new vocabulary through context clues while engaging in IDLE activities. For instance, Annika said, "I don't really follow-up on...searching that word, *gapamati lang ko sa context and daw ginapakot ko na lang Miss.*" (I just listen to the context, and I just guess the meaning.) Ismael

also reported, "Sometimes you would get it through context clues or what the topic is about, you can get context clues and sort of learn what the word is."

Two family members, a mother and a brother, confirmed this finding by saying that the students would figure out the meanings of new words via context clues. The mother of Clark said:

At times, even me, *basta may opportunity kami nga naga-watch* together, even I, *gapamangkot ko sa iya*. If he *hindi siya aware*, *gina-search gid ya namon*. *Dason gina-discuss man namon nga* "What does it mean?" "Sa context, *paano siya gingamit?*" (At times, even me, when we have the opportunity to watch together, even I ask him [the meaning of the word]. If he's not aware, we really discuss it. Then we discuss, "What does it mean?" "How is it used in context?")

Learning new words through context clues may be an example of a meaning-focused IDLE activity (Lee, 2017), which focuses "more on the fluency of authentic language use in unstructured, naturalistic digital settings (e.g., playing a multiplayer online game in English, or chatting via social media with other English users)" (p. 5). Some participants in this study appear to have learned new words in context while leisurely engaging in IDLE activities. These findings imply that the students understand the sentences in which the new words are used and can guess the meaning of new vocabulary without always using the dictionary (Davenport, 2018).

New Words Learned

A proof of how IDLE influenced vocabulary learning can be found in students' responses stating that they learned new words, as can be seen in Table 9. Eleven of them were able to cite new words, like "blasé" and "fortnight," that they were able to pick up from their IDLE activities, such as watching series, TikTok videos, and eBooks. Two of the family members were able to identify new words that the participants had learned, specifically "flamboyant" and "anti-Semitism." This "picking up" of new words may be supported by the theory of incidental learning (Hulstijn, 2013), which posits that learners can acquire words during everyday activities, without consciously intending to commit them to memory.

Table 9
Sample Words Learned Identified by Students

New Word(s) Learned	Source
blasé	9-1-1 television series
fortnight	<i>Game of Thrones</i> television series
apothecary	Unidentified movie
latter	Online Test
perspicacity	TikTok Account of Andrew Tate
arduous	<i>Art is Everything About You</i> book
abashed	<i>Song of Achilles</i> book
British English terms: fries are chips chips are crisps sneakers are trainers	Unidentified sources
opulence	<i>Drag Race Philippines</i> television series
milieu	Facebook Post
New Informal Word(s) Learned	Source
pooh-pooh	<i>The School for Good and Evil</i> book
ditto	Talking to international friends online
acronyms like BRB and AFK	Online Communication

Using New Words Learned

Another evidence of how IDLE affects vocabulary is how the learners use the new words they learned. Four of the participants expressed that when they encounter new words and get to know the meanings, they try to apply their learning in different situations, in either writing or speaking. For example, Vincent said:

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When seeing those words, I usually use the dictionary, *kag gina-input ko siya sa phone ko, gina search ko meaning sang amuni nga word* (I input the words in my phone and search the meaning)...and then I try to incorporate it sa when I speak, like if I discover a new word, I try to use it, or I think about it more often...Something in my head *lang* so that I will be familiar with the word, and then the next time when I see that word, or someone tells me that word, I'm familiar with it already and I can use that to understand the sentence.

It is apparent from this excerpt that the student does not just look up the meanings of new words, he also tries to incorporate them when he speaks. Other students had similar responses, like one who reported using new words in essays to make them sound more eloquent, and another who learned new English words from her online friends and started using them. Jennifer reported:

Kay na expose ko Miss sa social media and also my [online] friends, so ga-talk sila a lot of English, and they use also other English words nga daw, para sa akon, daw ka-deep, pero kay gina-use na nila, kabalo na ako kung paano i-use na in a sentence (I got exposed to social media and also my online friends who talk a lot in English, and they use other English words that are deep for me, but because they use them, I now know how to use them in a sentence.)

One family member expressed witnessing her sister using new words in conversations. Jennifer's sister said:

If *may bag-o nga na word na gin learn makadto na siya sa akon kag daw e recreate ya na or i-say it again niya sa akon ang amo na nga kind of phrase*

or word... *Makadto na siya sa akon kag gamiton ya na in a sentence...Parang daw ka gina make sure ya man guro nga chakto ang iya pronunciation. (If she learns a new word, she goes to me and tries to “recreate” it, or to say that word or phrase to me. She would go to me and use it in a sentence. It’s like she’s making sure that her pronunciation is correct.)*

It seems evident from this excerpt that the student would attempt to use new words while talking to her sister, using it in a sentence, and making sure that her pronunciation is correct. The results imply that the students’ vocabularies have widened their vocabulary because they are able to use new words in either speaking or writing. They understand their meanings well enough to be able to apply their knowledge in new spoken or written situations. Use of a vocabulary word is a strong measure of how well the learner understands the word (Dobbs & Kearns, 2016).

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students’ Writing Skills

The third research question also asked about the ways IDLE activities affect SHS students’ writing skills. The next section features the qualitative findings about IDLE and writing skills.

Learning from Models of Writing from IDLE

IDLE seems to have affected the writing skills of the students by giving them models for writing from the internet. For example, Abigail said:

I guess it's like when I'm writing I sometimes need to get inspiration on how to write something, so when I surf in the Internet I can just type, may it be

formal or informal, I just get ideas on how they construct their sentences or the paragraphs and try to put it into my writing file.

It seems evident from this excerpt that the student reads digital content and finds inspiration and models for writing while browsing through the internet. For example, she learns from how other writers construct their sentences and paragraphs.

Likewise, Agustin stated:

I also take information [for writing] from the internet, from what I see, how I develop the hooks, how I develop suspense, how I get people to have interest in my work, so I apply those [in my writing] and I take some inspiration from the internet.

According to Petelin (2021), reading exposes one to different writing styles, helps one to subconsciously learn syntax, grammar, style, punctuation, generic conventions, structure, and document design. The interview results suggest that Abigail and Agustin learned these while reading digital content. The results imply that by being immersed in written digital content, they may have “picked up” (Hulstijn, 2013) the writing styles of other authors, or they may also have deliberately searched how to write in certain styles. For them, learning to write through IDLE may have been incidental or intentional.

Moreover, because of IDLE, learners often develop a new identity as English users, not just learners (Lee, 2021). These students finding inspiration from the Internet for their own writing may be evidence of their being authentic English users.

Improving Writing through IDLE

Five participants talked about how IDLE improved their writing, with three saying that their writing is more concise and straightforward. For example, Clark reported:

I can say that now...my sentences are somewhat shorter. I use simpler terms now because before, I used to use very difficult words that would be very difficult for people to understand. I realized that in social media, most people only use simple terms in order to make sure that everyone can understand them. Because if they used [sic] very complex words, they sound too smart, too complicated, and it's just confusing.

It is apparent from this excerpt that the student learned how to use shorter sentences and simpler words so that he can be understood by his audience. He used social media as an example, where users would use simple terms. To find support for his answers, I revisited his essay response in the writing test (see Appendix H). He got an average score of 17 out of 20 points from the teacher-raters. His essay was indeed straightforward and had simple vocabulary, but he committed two errors, specifically in the use of an infinitive and a preposition. His satisfactory essay results substantiate his claim about his simple and straightforward writing, which may have been influenced by his engagement in IDLE.

On the other hand, the two expressed how they became more eloquent or sophisticated in their writing. For example, Vina said:

My sentences aren't as simple as they used to. I tend to describe events a little more, which could be a bit hifalutin, but I guess it's from the world-building and character-building in a book, but recently in school, when I

would write, it would definitely be more sophisticated compared to previous works.

To support Vina's claim, I also revisited her essay in the writing test (see Appendix I). She got an average score of 17.67 out of 20 points from the teacher-raters. Her essay is longer and more detailed than Clark's, with more supporting details in response to the prompt. Moreover, she used more advanced vocabulary, such as "enticing," "algorithm," "oblivious," and "inevitably." She only committed one error in the use of a verb. Her satisfactory essay results corroborate her claims that her writing has become sophisticated, which perhaps can be attributed to her engagement with IDLE.

Anya reported a similar experience, that watching many shows helped her writing sound more formal and eloquent. It is apparent from the reports of these two students that their writing became more complex and sophisticated after their engagement with IDLE. These students' experiences may again be evidence of the formation of their identity as English users, not just learners (Lee, 2021). From their exposure to online and digital content, they were able to develop their own styles of writing, such as being concise or being more sophisticated.

Becoming a Better Writer by Reading Digital Content

Among the different IDLE activities that the students claimed helped their writing, reading digital content in particular was identified by two students. They mentioned how reading digital content influenced the way they write. Eddie said:

I'm a reader *man daan* Miss. I like to read web novels and light novels. I

think that has helped me in writing as well, *kay* like as you read *daw gina*

copy *mo man bala kis-a ang ways sang author mag-write daw* like that (I'm a reader. I like to read web novels and light novels. I think that has helped me in writing as well, because as you read, you sometimes copy also the way the author writes.)

It seems evident from this excerpt that reading digital novels has influenced Eddie's writing because he imitates the way the author writes. Another student, Cristian, reported, "I think...many articles, many books I've read on the internet, have certainly attributed and impacted on the way I've been writing all my life."

Through reading, Eddie and Christian may have been exposed to different writing styles and may have subconsciously learned syntax, grammar, style, punctuation, generic conventions, structure, and document design (Petelin, 2021). They may have also been reading extensively, which is reading large amounts of text for enjoyment, which, in turn, could have influenced their writing (Robb, 2018). Through extensive reading, they may have learned the skills necessary for writing, like vocabulary and grammar (Johansson, 2014; Ewert, 2019).

Learning Punctuations from the Internet

When asked for an example of something they have encountered on the internet and how this helped improve their writing, ten participants cited how they learned punctuations. Five students mentioned the Oxford comma, while a participant's brother likewise mentioned the Oxford comma. One said that she learned to avoid using the Oxford comma from the internet. Others mentioned the semicolon and the em-dash.

Table 10
Punctuations Learned Identified by Students

Punctuation Learned	Function
Oxford comma	Comma placed before the conjunction at the end of a list of things to avoid ambiguity in sentences (TELC, 2017).
Semicolon	Joins two related independent clauses in place of a comma and a coordinating conjunction (Northern Illinois University, n.d.).
Colon	Used to give emphasis, present dialogue, introduce lists or text, and clarify composition titles (Western Michigan University, n.d.).
Em-dash	Used to mark a break in a sentence (Luo, 2019).

The results imply that the learners may have incidentally learned how certain punctuations are used in digital text, and could have used these in their own writing. These results are comparable to Aka's (2020) study, which studied the effects of incidental learning of one specific grammatical feature through reading. They may also have intentionally looked up how these punctuations are used before using them. According to Lee (2021), informally learning English through digital means can happen incidentally and/or intentionally.

Writing Facilitated by Interactive Reading and Writing

Two participants talked about how their writing has been facilitated by IDLE, specifically writing assistant tools (e.g., Grammarly and Quillbot) and the online word processor Google Docs. For instance, Vincent said:

I can really say *daw dako gid ang bulig sang mga internet and mga digital devices* when I write, especially Grammarly *nga daw ga-suggest siya bala ang ano dapat ang mga words sulaton mo, ano dapat ang sentence mo,* and *daw naanad ko bala Miss nga may guide siya, na daw ga-guide siya sa akon* when I write an essay. *Halin sang pagsugod bala sako writing bala,* I think that was 2020...*ga-Google na lang ko, ang Grammarly, naanad ko Miss nga may dictionary ko, para macheck ko, mga thesaurus bala...if wala na sila,* I mean *kaya man, pero not too confident lang.* (I can really say that the internet and digital devices have really helped me when I write, especially Grammarly that suggests what should be the words that you write, and it guides me when I write an essay. When I got busy writing, I think that was 2020, I just used Google, Grammarly, and I got used to the dictionary, so that I could check, and the thesaurus. If I don't have these, I can [write], but I won't be too confident.)

It seems evident from this excerpt that Vincent uses online and digital technologies like Google, Grammarly, the online dictionary, and the thesaurus to help him write confidently. One parent affirmed this, as she cited how an app helped her son rephrase his writing and use alternative words. This result may be related to Shafirova and Cassany's (2019) study which cited technology such as Google Docs as an effective tool for English language learners.

It may be possible that Vincent has become dependent on these digital resources to be able to write effectively. He did mention that he lacks confidence when he does not have these. The findings suggest that young people may rely heavily on digital technologies to aid them in their writing, which is helpful because it allows them

to improve and substantiate their written work. However, this behavior could also have negative effects because they may not be able to formulate independent, original thought.

English Learned through IDLE as “Informal”

A key finding in this study is how four participants mentioned that much of the English they learned online is informal. Three described it as “slang,” with words like acronyms such as BRB (“be right back”) and AFK (“away from keyboard”). Others said that they observed a lot of shortcuts and misplaced words in English. As Ismael puts it:

Online learning in English is mostly entertainment, it's more of the slang portion of English. You won't find many straight English, all English in its correct grammar, correct pronunciation, and all that, but the majority of what you would find would be more on how people talk to each other or the slang culture of English, and you would see a lot of shortcuts, a lot of misplaced words here and there.

Ismael observed that much of the English learned online is slang or informal, with many errors. This excerpt can be explained by another finding of this study, that the students spend the most time on social media. The English language on social media has a lot of errors and can negatively affect grammar, spelling, and sentence construction (Saha, 2019). Perhaps the participants have been exposed to the mistakes of the English language which, in turn, may affect their written and spoken English.

Another student even said how he found himself using informal shortcuts in formal writing that he learned from the internet, and that he had to correct himself:

Ga-effect man gid sa akon [ang internet], like when I'm chatting, gausar ko gid mga shortcut nga words, and kung magsulat ko bi, like something for school, gakalipat ko gali that I'm using shortcut terms, so I have to pangita ang original version. Kay daw gakalipat ko bala, ay daw ka unformal gali nga words, so I have to use the formal term for it. (The internet has affected the way I write, like when I'm chatting, I use shortcuts of words, and when I write, like something for school, I forget that I'm using shortcut terms, so I have to search for the original version. I forget that these words are informal, so I have to use the formal term for it.)

One parent affirmed this and said that her son noticed that his peers use shortcuts and do not observe proper grammar and spelling:

Kung ma-observe ta, lain ang lenguahe sang generation subung. Oftentimes, I would often hear [my son's] comment nga kung kis-a bala ang iban niya nga mga kilala, or even his contemporaries, when they communicate let's say, sa social media, maskin gaistoryahanay lang, he notices nga hindi na gid proper ang pag-observe sang mga grammar and even spelling. Amona ang ma-notice subung, mahilig kita mag-shortcut. Amuna ang ma-observe niya, nga somehow, ang iban hindi na very particular about that, proper observance of grammar and spelling when they communicate, most especially in social media. So I guess ang iya nga na-notice that particular gap, na daw ka kakulangan sang pag-communicate nila, that makes him even more conscious to phrase sang iya ginahambal

properly. *Nakita niya ang limitation o kakulangan, amuna ang nagabulig sa iya para nga sa iya nga writing, he would be more mindful and conscious and aware of using the proper grammar and syntax, kay tungod nga nakita niya nga sa iban, hindi inchakto.* (If we observe, the language of this generation is different. Oftentimes, I would often hear [my son's] comment that the people he knows, or even his contemporaries, when they communicate, let's say, on social media, even when just conversing, he notices that they don't observe proper grammar and even spelling. It's noticeable that we like using shortcuts. That's what he observed, that somehow, some people are not very particular about that, the proper observance of grammar and spelling when they communicate, especially on social media. He notices that particular gap, that limitation, in their communication, that makes him even more conscious to phrase what he says properly. He saw the limitations, which helped him in his writing; he would be more mindful and conscious and aware of using the proper grammar and syntax, because he observed that the others do not.)

The results show that students can distinguish between formal and informal English. It also appears as if the exposure to informal language may have affected the formal writing of a learner. Informal online language is often used by Generation Z (Hart, 2022; Seariac, 2022), where the participants belong. Learning informal English may be beneficial to second language learners as it prepares them for casual and spontaneous communication in either writing or conversations. It can be used when writing personal messages and its tone is more personal than formal language (University of Technology Sydney, 2022). However, informal English on the Internet

also has many abbreviations, misspelled words, grammatical and spelling mistakes which are committed by young people.

The findings imply immersion in English digital content, especially social media, is not always beneficial. It exposes the student to many errors in the English language, as well as informal online language. These errors may affect formal, academic writing.

Synthesis

The third research question asked about the ways IDLE activities affect SHS students' vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. The qualitative results show how their IDLE activities influence their vocabulary knowledge, particularly when the students would learn new words by looking up the meanings or learn them in context. They cited new words that they had learned from their engagement in IDLE, and mentioned how they would use the new words they had learned in either speaking or writing.

The findings also show how their IDLE activities affect their writing skills because they learn models of writing from digital content. They also claim that they have improved their writing through IDLE and through reading digital content. Moreover, they cited specific punctuations they had learned from the internet, and said that their writing has been facilitated by interactive reading and writing.

A significant finding in this study is how participants reported that much of the English learned online is informal, with slang words and errors. While learning informal English is beneficial for casual contexts, its errors may affect the formal, academic writing of the learners.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the IDLE activities of Filipino senior high school students, the correlation of the time spent on IDLE activities and (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance, and how IDLE activities affect vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of the participants. In summary, the results show that Filipino senior high school students engage in a variety of IDLE activities, but the time they spend on these has no significant correlation with their vocabulary or writing performance. In the qualitative phase of the study, selected participants also cited the different ways how IDLE activities had affected their vocabulary knowledge and writing skills. In this section, I highlight the key findings of the research and give the conclusions and recommendations for future research, teaching, and parental involvement.

Summary of Findings

Informal Digital Learning of English of Filipino Senior High School Students

The results showed that they engage in a variety of IDLE activities, namely using social media, watching videos, listening to music, playing digital games, reading digital content, and other IDLE activities such as podcasts and video calls. The participants reported spending the most time on social media, followed by videos, other IDLE activities (e.g., podcasts and voice/video calls), music, digital games, and lastly, reading. The qualitative data revealed that the participants report improving their English and learning new words from social media, videos, and reading online and digital content. Moreover, the results show that the participants multitask when

listening to music while doing other tasks, and having voice or video calls via Discord when playing online games. Another key finding is that the parents support and regulate the participants' IDLE activities, which was manifested in buying gadgets for their children, exposing their children to English media from an early age, and discussing new words or articles found on the internet or movies.

IDLE and Vocabulary Performance and Writing Performance

I also asked whether there is a correlation between the time SHS students spend on IDLE activities and their (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance. After administering a survey questionnaire and vocabulary and writing tests, and analyzing the data, I found that the time spent on IDLE activities does not have a significant correlation with either the vocabulary scores or writing scores, which confirm the null hypotheses that there are no significant relationships between time spent on IDLE and vocabulary performance and writing performance, respectively.

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students' Vocabulary Knowledge

To answer the third research question about how IDLE activities affect SHS students' vocabulary knowledge, I conducted interviews among selected participants who had reported a high amount of time in IDLE activities and garnered the highest scores in the vocabulary and writing tests. They reported form-focused IDLE activities, such as searching for meanings of unfamiliar words online, as well as meaning-focused activities, like reading online content and watching videos, from which some claimed they learned new words in context. Although the quantitative data shows that there is no significant relationship between time spent on IDLE and vocabulary

performance, the qualitative data shows that the participants engage in a combination of form- and meaning-focused activities which may have led to their vocabulary learning, similar to the results of Lee (2017).

How IDLE Activities Affect SHS Students' Writing Skills

The third research question also asked about how IDLE activities affect SHS students' writing skills. The interview participants reported how they were able to find models for writing from the internet, and how they improved their writing through IDLE, either with their writing becoming concise and straightforward, or more eloquent and sophisticated. The participants also expressed how they became better writers because of the digital content they read, which may be attributed to extensive reading. Another noteworthy finding is that many participants cited learning punctuations from IDLE, such as the Oxford comma, the semicolon and the em-dash. Even with these qualitative results that show that the interview participants had learned English skills through IDLE, the quantitative results indicate that there is no significant relationship between time spent on IDLE and writing performance. The test ratings show that the students generally had unsatisfactory scores in the criterion of sentence structure, grammar, mechanics, and spelling. This could be attributed to four interview participants' observations that young people are exposed to informal English or slang, which compose a significant part of the internet and contain many errors in the English language. Exposure to slang or informal English online may increase grammatical errors in writing, although more research needs to be done to validate this.

Conclusions

This research aimed to identify the IDLE activities of Filipino senior high school students, examine the relationship between the time spent on IDLE activities and (a) vocabulary performance and (b) writing performance, and how IDLE activities affect vocabulary knowledge and writing skills of the participants.

It can be concluded that just like other countries (e.g., Korea, Denmark, Sweden) where IDLE has been studied, various IDLE activities have reportedly influenced the learning of English of Filipino SHS learners. Digital activities like using social media and watching videos are not just leisure activities, but useful resources for English language learning. Filipino ESL students can turn to these to supplement their learning of the language at school. For example, when they encounter unfamiliar words in English videos or digital books, they may take note of these and look up their meanings online afterwards. They may also multitask by, for instance, watching a movie while reading the English subtitles.

This thesis has also shown that the more time spent on IDLE activities does not predict gains in vocabulary development, but the kind of IDLE activities can. Simply allowing learners to immerse themselves in IDLE activities for long periods of time does not directly result in vocabulary growth (Lee, 2019). Rather, to develop their vocabulary, learners can engage in a variety of form-focused activities (e.g., looking up definitions of words in a dictionary) and meaning-focused activities (e.g., learning words in context). The findings of this study imply that IDLE has the potential to contribute to vocabulary development, although the quantity (measured in time) does not predict it.

This study likewise reveals that the more time spent on IDLE activities does not predict gains in writing development. While learners can find models or exemplars of good writing on the internet and other digital content, they may also be exposed to informal English and its errors, which may affect their formal, academic writing. This study implies that IDLE may have a positive influence on writing development, but it may also negatively affect it due to the errors in English and the informal language found on the internet and other digital media.

Recommendations

Based on these conclusions, I make the following recommendations:

ESL Learners

Aside from seeing IDLE activities as a form of leisure, Filipino students can view them as a way to augment their learning of English and be more intentional in utilizing these activities. For example, when watching a series, a learner can go beyond being entertained and use the activity as an opportunity to pick up new English words and idioms.

To supplement their vocabulary development, they can engage in a variety of form- and meaning-focused language learning through IDLE to increase their vocabulary learning. Examples of form-focused IDLE activities include using an eReader to annotate and look up unfamiliar words in a book or using Google to find synonyms of a word. Examples of meaning-focused activities range from watching educational videos on YouTube for leisure or chatting via social media with other English users, among other activities that involve authentic language use. Learners can expose themselves to IDLE activities with more sophisticated vocabulary that they

have not tried before, such as educational podcasts. Moreover, they can learn how to distinguish formal English from informal or slang forms they find online so they can minimize errors in formal academic writing.

ESL Teachers

English teachers can integrate IDLE activities more deliberately and intentionally in teaching vocabulary and writing. For example, they can utilize YouTube videos or Netflix series to teach new words, or incorporate social media into the writing tasks that they assign to their students. They can also get online news articles or opinion editorials as models of good writing for the students to study. Incorporating IDLE into English lessons can make them more relevant and interesting for the ESL learners.

Parents

As the primary educators of their children, parents have a key role in supporting their children's engagement in IDLE activities. Even if their children are already in high school, parents can continue participating in the language and literacy development of their children. They can accompany their children as they engage in different IDLE activities such as watching television series or listening to podcasts, and discuss with them what new words or other elements of English they learned from these. Moreover, parents can give their children opportunities to apply what they have learned from IDLE through the practice of speaking and writing in English at home. Parents can also be more aware of what kinds of online or digital content their children consume (e.g., YouTube channels) as these may include informal or erroneous English, which

may need to be corrected. However, they should also regulate their children's IDLE use by placing limits on IDLE activities, as too much screen time has harmful effects on young people (Serrano, 2022).

Future Research

To better understand the implications of these results, future research can be done to:

1. further validate the relationship between IDLE and vocabulary and writing by conducting research on the same topic on other Filipino participants of different age groups and socioeconomic profiles. The results may be different, for example, if a similar study was conducted among public school students.
2. use different research instruments to conduct future studies on the topic. The Productive Vocabulary Levels Test used for this study, although widely used in previous studies, was developed in the 1990s. Perhaps a more recent vocabulary test would yield different findings.
3. find whether there is a relationship between IDLE and other language outcomes among Filipino students, such as reading comprehension and speaking.
4. determine the relationship of IDLE on student writing and its errors through a writing test by investigating the correlation between time spent on IDLE and the number of errors in sentence structure, grammar, mechanics, and spelling.
5. conduct qualitative studies about parental influence on their children's IDLE activities, such as investigating parents' motivations and practices in supporting and regulating this kind of learning. It would be interesting to study why and how parents would encourage or limit their children's IDLE activities.

6. investigate how multitasking in IDLE influences English language learning. Researchers can find whether there is a correlation between students' self-reported multitasking behavior and their English language proficiency.

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Appendix A: Letter to the Principal

April 27, 2022

██████████
School Principal
██████████

Dear Dr. ██████████

Greetings! I would like to ask your permission to conduct a survey, vocabulary and writing tests, and interviews among the Senior High School students of ██████████. The results will be used in my thesis, "Informal Digital Learning of English of Filipino High School Students" for my Master's degree in Language and Literacy Education at UPOU. I am investigating how SHS students learn English outside school using the internet and other digital technologies, and how this learning relates to their vocabulary and writing.

Administering the survey and the tests will be done online and will take 45 minutes, while each interview will last 30 minutes. Attached are the research instruments for this study. I would like to ask if I can pilot test these to 8 SHS students in May before the report card distribution. I also plan to do trial interviews with two of the students and their parents.

After the research instruments are finalized, I would also like to ask your approval to conduct the actual data gathering for the study among the incoming Grade 11 and 12 students in August 2022. I intend to do this in batches during the students' available times. I can coordinate with the Senior High School Department Head about the schedules. After the quantitative data has been collected and analyzed, I plan to interview 20 selected participants and their parents.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary; I will ask the consent of all the respondents before collecting data. There are no known or anticipated risks. All information provided will be kept confidential and will only be used for academic purposes. The names of respondents and of the school will not appear in the thesis or publications resulting from this study.

Once the study is concluded, you will receive a copy of the executive summary. I can also provide a PDF of the entire final thesis upon request.

If you agree, kindly sign below acknowledging your consent and permission for me to conduct the pilot tests and the data gathering for my thesis at your school. Your approval to conduct this study will be appreciated. Thank you, and I hope for a positive response from you.

Sincerely,
Maria Alexia A. Adizon
UPOU Student
09177091065
aaadizon@up.edu.ph

Noted by:

Prof. Nerissa O. Zara
Thesis Adviser
UPOU Affiliate Professor

Appendix B: Parental Consent for the Participation in the Study

Greetings! My name is Maria Alexia A. Adizon, a Master's student at the University of the Philippines Open University and a former teacher of St. John's Institute. I would like to invite your child to participate in the research study entitled "Informal Digital Learning of English of Filipino High School Students."

I am investigating how senior high school students learn English outside school using the internet and other digital technologies, and how this learning relates to their vocabulary and writing. Because your child is an English as second language learner (ESL) and a current SHS student, he/she fits the criteria for this study.

If you agree to let him/her to be part of this study, I will ask him/her to answer the following:

1. A survey questionnaire asking him/her how much time he/she spends on online and digital activities in English
2. A vocabulary test
3. A writing test that asks him/her to respond to a YouTube video about social media

I may also invite ask him/her to an interview to find out in depth how he/she learns English through the internet and other digital technologies. All surveys, tests, and interviews will be done online, via Google Meet.

Your child's information will be kept strictly confidential. Their responses and interview recordings will be deleted immediately after the conclusion of the study.

You have the right to refuse to allow your child to participate or to withdraw him/her at any time, without penalty. If your child does withdraw, it will not affect you or your child in any way. If you or your child chooses to withdraw, any data which has been collected from your child will be destroyed.

There are no foreseen risks in participating in this study. While there are no benefits, payments, or incentives for this study, your child may contribute to finding new ways to improve English teaching and learning in the Philippine setting.

I have read the information in this consent form.

- I allow my child to participate in this research project.
- I do not allow my child to participate in this research project.

Child's Full Name: _____

Parent's Full Name: _____

Appendix C: Questionnaire for the Students

Greetings! My name is Maria Alexia A. Adizon and I'm currently studying for a Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education at the University of the Philippines Open University.

I am studying how Senior High School students learn English outside school using the internet, smartphones, laptops, and other digital technologies. I also want to discover if this kind of learning has a relationship with their vocabulary and writing performance. I would like to invite you to be part of this study. Answering the questionnaire and the tests will take less than an hour.

Participation is completely voluntary and you can withdraw at any time for any reason. You will be asked to write your name because I may invite you to an interview afterwards. However, your identity and your school's name will be kept confidential. If you do participate, you will contribute to finding new ways to improve English teaching and learning for students like you.

I consent to participate in this research.

Yes No

1. Your Name:

(This is required because you may be invited for an interview afterwards.)

2. Grade:

11 12

3. Age

16 17 18 19

4. Sex Assigned at Birth

Male Female

5. Strand:

- Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM)
- Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM)
- Humanities and Social Sciences Strand (HUMSS)

6. Please estimate how many hours daily you spend doing each activity in English during your free time.

(These activities should be done outside school and are not related to classroom learning, so extracurricular activities and homework are not included.)

Activity	Time Spent
<p>Videos Watching online films, videos, series, and streaming services (e.g. Netflix, YouTube)</p>	
<p>Social Media communicating on social media sites (e.g. Tiktok, Instagram, Twitter, Reddit)</p>	
<p>Music Listening to music with English lyrics (e.g. Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube Music)</p>	
<p>Digital Gaming Playing mobile, online, PC, console games, or other digital games (e.g. Mobile Legends, Genshin Impact, League of Legends)</p>	
<p>Reading Reading online content from websites or ebooks (e.g. Kindle eBooks, Wikipedia articles, news websites like Rappler and Inquirer)</p>	
<p>Social Reading Platforms Reading and/or writing on social reading platforms (e.g. Wattpad)</p>	
<p>Other Online and/or Digital Activities in English: Please enumerate other online and/or digital activities in English you do during your free time. Estimate the number of hours you spend daily for each activity. <i>Examples:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Listening to English podcasts - 1 hour,</i> ● <i>Taking online courses in English for leisure - 2 hours</i> ● <i>Voice or video calls with other people in English using messaging platforms like Messenger, Discord, Whatsapp, and Viber - 1 hour</i> <p>a. b. c.</p>	

Appendix D: Productive Vocabulary Levels Test

Instructions:

Complete the sentence by writing the whole word in its grammatically correct form.

Example: The garden was full of fra__ flowers.

Answer: fragrant

Limit yourself to 20 minutes when answering this test. Please refrain from using Google or any kind of dictionary or search engine.

1. In their geography class, the children are doing a special pro__ on North America.
2. The drug was introduced after medical res__ indisputably proved its effectiveness.
3. The job sounded interesting at first, but when he realized what it involved, his excitement sub__.
4. There has been a recent tr__ among prosperous families toward a smaller number of children.
5. A considerable amount of evidence was accum__ during the investigation.
6. The urge to survive is inh__ in all creatures.
7. She was sitting on a balcony and bas__ in the sun.
8. Anyone found loo__ bombed houses and shops will be severely punished.
9. The wounded man squi__ on the floor in agony.
10. The rescue attempt could not proceed quickly. It was imp__ by bad weather.
11. We could hear the sergeant bel__ commands to the troops.
12. The building is heated by a modern heating appa__.
13. He is so depressed that he is cont__ suicide.
14. He perc__ a light at the end of the tunnel.
15. The pro__ of failing the test scared him.
16. The differences were so sl__ that they went unnoticed.
17. For many people, wealth is a prospect of unimaginable felic__.
18. The floor in the ballroom was a mos__ of pastel colours.
19. The dog crin__ when it saw the snake.
20. She showed off her sle__ figure in a long narrow dress.

Answer Key

1. In their geography class, the children are doing a special pro__ on North America.
(project)
2. The drug was introduced after medical res__ indisputably proved its effectiveness.
(research)
3. The job sounded interesting at first, but when he realized what it involved, his excitement sub__.
(subsided)

4. There has been a recent tr____ among prosperous families toward a smaller number of children. **(trend)**
5. A considerable amount of evidence was accum____ during the investigation. **(accumulated)**
6. The urge to survive is inh____ in all creatures. **(inherent)**
7. She was sitting on a balcony and bas____ in the sun. **(basked)**
8. Anyone found loo____ bombed houses and shops will be severely punished. **(looting)**
9. The wounded man squi____ on the floor in agony. **(squirmed)**
10. The rescue attempt could not proceed quickly. It was imp____ by bad weather. **(impeded)**
11. We could hear the sergeant bel____ commands to the troops. **(bellowing)**
12. The building is heated by a modern heating appa____. **(apparatus)**
13. He is so depressed that he is cont____ suicide. **(contemplating)**
14. He perc____ a light at the end of the tunnel. **(perceived)**
15. The pro____ of failing the test scared him. **(prospect)**
16. The differences were so sl____ that they went unnoticed. **(slight)**
17. For many people, wealth is a prospect of unimaginable felic____. **(felicity)**
18. The floor in the ballroom was a mos____ of pastel colours. **(mosaic)**
19. The dog crin____ when it saw the snake. **(cringed)**
20. She showed off her sle____ figure in a long narrow dress. **(slender)**

Appendix E: Writing Test

First Version:

Watch the video, "Are You Living an Insta Lie? Social Media Vs. Reality":
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0EFHbruKEmw>

Write an essay answering the question below. Support your answer with personal experiences. Please refrain from using Google or any other resources.

Please try to limit yourself to 40 minutes to plan, write and revise your essay. The essay must have a minimum of 300 words or 15-20 sentences.

How do you feel about using social media after watching this video? Please share the positive and negative effects of social media on your life.

Second Version:

Watch the video, "Why We Can't Stop Scrolling":
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uBkeKv_6U4c

Write an essay answering the question below. Support your answer with examples and personal experiences. Please refrain from using Google or any other resources.

Please try to limit yourself to 40 minutes to plan, write and revise your essay. The essay must have a minimum of 300 words or 15-20 sentences.

How do you feel about the time you spend on online activities (e.g. social media, gaming) after watching this video? What advice would you give to someone with an internet addiction?

Essay Rubrics: The rubric rating were done by the researcher and two experienced English teachers. Their scores were computed to determine inter-rater reliability.

Traits	4	3	2	1
Focus	The essay is focused, purposeful, and reflects clear insight and ideas.	The essay is focused on the topic and includes relevant ideas.	The essay is focused on the topic and includes a few loosely related ideas.	The essay poorly addresses topic and includes irrelevant ideas.
Support	The author persuasively supports the main point with well-developed reasons and/or examples.	The author supports the main point with developed reasons and/or examples.	The author supports the main point with some underdeveloped reasons and/or examples.	The author provides little or no support for the main point.
Organization	The author effectively organizes ideas to build a logical, coherent essay.	The author organizes ideas to build an essay.	The author uses some organization of ideas to build an essay.	The author uses little or no organization of ideas to build an essay.
Word Choice	The author uses vivid words and phrases. The choice and placement of words seems accurate, natural, and not forced.	The author uses vivid words and phrases. The choice and placement of words is inaccurate at times and/or seems overdone.	The author uses words that communicate clearly, but the writing lacks variety.	The writer uses a limited vocabulary. Jargon or clichés may be present and detract from the meaning.
Sentence Structure, Grammar, Mechanics, & Spelling	All sentences are well constructed and have varied structure and length. The author makes no errors in grammar, mechanics, and/or spelling.	Most sentences are well constructed and have varied structure and length. The author makes a few errors in grammar, mechanics, and/or spelling, but they do not interfere with understanding.	Most sentences are well constructed, but they have a similar structure and/or length. The author makes several errors in grammar, mechanics, and/or spelling that interfere with understanding.	Sentences sound awkward, are distractingly repetitive, or are difficult to understand. The author makes numerous errors in grammar, mechanics, and/or spelling that interfere with understanding.

References for the Essay Rubric:

Kwantlen Polytechnic University. (n.d.). *Rubric for Essay: High School*. Retrieved April 23, 2022, from <https://www.kpu.ca/sites/default/files/NEVR/High%20School%20Rubrics.pdf>

Read Write Think. (2013). *Essay Rubric*. Retrieved April 23, 2022, from <https://www.readwritethink.org/sites/default/files/Essay%20Rubric.pdf>

Appendix F: Interview Release Form

I understand that Maria Alexia A. Adizon is preparing, writing, and will publish her thesis "Informal Digital Learning of English of Filipino High School Students." In order to assist the Author in the preparation of the Work, I have agreed to be interviewed and to provide information to be used in connection with the Work, including my personal experiences, remarks, and recollections.

I hereby grant and assign to the Author the following rights in connection with the Interview Materials for use as part of the thesis:

The right to quote or paraphrase all or any portion of the Interview Materials, and to generally use and publish the Interview Materials, including my experiences, recollections, incidents, remarks, dialogue, and information.

In order to enable the Author to develop the thesis in any manner that she may deem best, I hereby release and discharge the Author from any and all claims, demands, or causes of action that I may have against them by reason of anything contained in the Work, or any of the above uses.

I understand that my identity and the school's name will be kept anonymous. I also understand that my participation is voluntary and I may stop at any time I feel uncomfortable.

I have read and understood this agreement. This Agreement expresses the complete understanding of the parties.

Email: _____

Name: _____

Date Submitted: _____

Appendix G: Interview Protocols

I. Interview Protocol for the Students

Introductory Protocol

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. My name is Lex Adizon, the researcher of this study. To facilitate my note-taking, I will record this conversation. Please sign the release form. Only I will have access to the recording, which will eventually be deleted after it is transcribed.

You must sign a form to meet our ethical requirements. Essentially, this document states that (1) the information from this interview may be included in my research, but (2) your identity will be kept confidential, (3) your participation is voluntary and you may stop at any time you feel uncomfortable.

This interview will last less than 30 minutes.

Purpose

I am currently conducting a study about how SHS students learn English outside school using the internet and other digital technologies, and how this learning relates to their vocabulary and writing. These are not related to classroom learning, so extracurricular activities and homework are not included.

I would like to ask some questions about how you learned English outside of school using the internet and digital technology, and how these activities have influenced your vocabulary and writing.

Body.

1. How do you think using the internet and digital devices has affected your English skills?
(Examples of these activities include online videos, social media, online music streaming, digital gaming, reading online content or ebooks, and social reading platforms, use of smartphones, tablets, and laptops)
2. Can you describe how you learn new vocabulary from the internet and digital devices? Can you share something you've recently watched or read on the internet in the past 6 months and what new words you learned?
3. Can you describe how your writing is affected by your use of the internet and digital devices? Can you share an example of something you've encountered on the internet in the past 6 months and how this helped improve your writing?

Closing

Thank you for sharing your experiences! I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know?

I should have all the information I need. Would it be all right for me to contact you if I have any more questions? Thanks again.

II. Interview Protocol for the Family Members

Introductory Protocol

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. My name is Lex Adizon, the researcher of this study. To facilitate my note-taking, I will record this conversation. Please sign the release form. Only I will have access to the recording, which will eventually be deleted after it is transcribed.

You must sign a form to meet our ethical requirements. Essentially, this document states that (1) the information from this interview may be included in my research, but (2) your identity will be kept confidential, (3) your participation is voluntary and you may stop at any time you feel uncomfortable.

This interview will last less than 30 minutes.

Purpose

I am currently conducting a study about how SHS students learn English outside school using the internet and other digital technologies, and how this learning relates to their vocabulary and writing. These are not related to classroom learning, so extracurricular activities and homework are not included.

I would like to ask some questions about how your child/sibling/cousin learned English outside of school using the internet and digital technology. I also would like to ask how these activities have influenced their vocabulary and writing.

Body.

1. How do you think your child/sibling/cousin's English skills were affected by his/her use of the internet and digital devices?

(Examples of these activities include online videos, social media, online music streaming, digital gaming, reading online content or ebooks, and social reading platforms, use of smartphones, tablets, and laptops)

2. Can you describe how your child/sibling/cousin learns new vocabulary from the internet and digital devices? Can you share something he/she has watched or read on the internet in the past 6 months and what new words he/she learned?
3. Can you describe how your child/sibling/cousin's writing is affected by his/her use of the internet and digital devices? Can you share an example of something he/she encountered on the internet in the past 6 months and how this helped improve his/her writing?

Closing

Thank you for sharing your child's learning experiences! I appreciate the time you took for this interview. Is there anything else you think would be helpful for me to know?

I should have all the information I need. Would it be all right for me to contact you if I have any more questions? Thanks again.

Appendix H: Clark's Essay

In the video, it is stated that one scrolls through social media until they find something interesting. They would then react to it by either showing emotions like laughing or reacting to a post by liking or sharing it. As we can see, this can prove to be addicting and very time consuming. Eventually, it becomes a habit as it feels automatic and something done in constant repetition. We eventually spend so much time that if we thought we spent 15 minutes scrolling, we would have actually used up double that time.

This hurts our time management significantly. For example, if one wakes up at 6:00 AM and needs to be somewhere by 8, they could plan to spend 5 minutes of their time on Facebook in order to get a quick laugh. They think they only spent five minutes on the site, but in reality, it's already 7:00. They realize this and they begin to rush, which means they are not as prepared as they would like to going to that place. They can either be late, or look unprepared.

I am also quite guilty of this. I would normally scroll Twitter before sleep (I plan to sleep to 10:30) but slept 15 minutes later than planned. This affects my sleep as I would wake up slightly less energized, which goes a long way.

I would suggest limiting yourself from social media once in a while and have fun with other things. Go outside, exercise, touch some grass. Or even better, talk to someone in real life. But whatever you do, make sure to have fun.

Appendix I: Vina's Essay

I honestly feel that I am more knowledgeable about why social media is addicting. Social media is a big part of people's lives nowadays because it is an easy and instant form of communication, entertainment and even plays a big part in businesses especially those in the smaller scale. It rewards the users with content that they want to see at random making it more enticing. It also uses an algorithm or pattern that is customised to each individual user so that they would be more interested in what they have to offer. New job opportunities like social media management and content creators have risen in popularity with the hopes of going viral or being the next big thing. Admittedly, it has also helped bring awareness to multiple causes that are important to some individuals and has helped enlighten those oblivious to them. It has also raise funds for those in need especially during the pandemic. Strangers from across the globe can connect and bond over common interests making the internet more appealing especially towards the younger generations.

Being addicted to the internet is sadly a very common problem right now considering that it is used everyday for work, school and leisure. The advice I would give if you are struggling with addiction is to set boundaries and limits and if you can go on a ""detox"" from the internet. Setting boundaries and limits can help you manage your time and slowly step away from the temptation. You can do activities or chores that do not need the use of the internet in the meantime while you let your mind refresh itself and allow you to concentrate on what you are doing. Going on a ""detox"" from the internet is a little more extreme than setting boundaries because you would be away from it for an extended period of time. Of course you would not be able to cut it off for the rest of your life because you would inevitably have to use it but if you can it would be nice to go somewhere where the internet is weak or slow like the mountains every once in a while so you could truly step back and be able to help your addiction.